

Landscape analysis for the packaging specification and components

Types, Tools, Platforms, and Packages

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Abstract

A review of the design considerations, standards, specifications, and important implementations that apply to File Type registries, definition and harvesting of file types in repositories, Tools and Workflow Registries, and the inventorisation and description of Platforms for processing of data. An information model is derived to describe the definitions and interrelationships between the actors, concepts, and objects that are in scope for these topics, and the recommendations define the scope of work required for implementation by work packages and participating repositories in the EOSC Data Commons project.

The work is a foundational input to the objective of automating the matching of datasets with applicable tools and workflows, and automation of its deployment to platforms that can support its execution.

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Acronyms

Note on MIME Types: IANA defined MIME types¹ as a mechanism for identifying different media being transmitted over the internet, but has subsequently changed the label to 'Media Types'. We use the older 'MIME Types' in this document since it remains in common use and the term is more familiar.

AIP	Archival Information Package
API	Application Programming Interface
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
BPEL	Business Process Execution Language
CCSDS	Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems
CNRI	Corporation for National Research Initiatives
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CTS	CoreTrustSeal
CWL	Common Workflow Language
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DIP	Dissemination Information Package
DoA	Description of Action - from project proposal
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTR	Data Type Registry
EDAM	Ontology of bioscientific data analysis and data management
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Media_type

FTP/ FTPS	File Transfer Protocol/ Secure Version
GCS	Google Cloud Services
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP, HTTPS	Hypertext Text Transfer Protocol/ Secure Version
IANA	Internet Assigned Numbers Authority
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPFS	InterPlanetary File System
ISA	Instruction Set Architecture
ISO	International Standards Organisation
LLM	Large Language Model
METS	Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard
MIME	Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions
OAIS-RM	Open Archival Information Systems Reference Model
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations
PID	Persistent Identifier
RAM	Random Access Memory
RoR	Research Organisation Registry, a PID for research organisations
RRID	Research Resource Identifier
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SIP	Submission Information Package
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
VM	Virtual Machine
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WDL	Workflow Description Language
XML	Extended Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

Executive Summary

This report is a review of the design considerations, standards, specifications, and important implementations that apply to File Type registries, definition and harvesting of file types in repositories, Tools and Workflow Registries, and the inventorisation and description of Platforms for processing of data. These registries are collectively referred to as the 'Catalogue of Tools'.

The definition of the package contents to indicate data and tools to be deployed to platforms ('Request Packager') is also reviewed.

The work is a foundational input to the objective of automating the matching of datasets with applicable tools and workflows ('Matchmaker' capabilities), and automation of its deployment to platforms that can support its execution ('Data Player' capabilities) via content described in the Request Packager.

The report is based largely on a desktop study of relevant sources, its analysis, and a synthesis of the implications for the encoding and management of inventories of file types, tools and workflows, and platforms, and the packages to be deployed to platforms. Some inputs have been obtained already from use case participants in the project, but significant contributions to the contents of these inventories is expected in the next round of work, which involves development of specification(s) (September 2025), and Proof-of-Concept implementations (November 2025) for the main components.

The main components and supporting applications and/ or registry databases are reviewed in dedicated chapters:

- Chapter 3: A review of the exchange package landscape, both from a trustworthy repository and computational/ workflow perspective.
- Chapter 4: File types and type registries, and an analysis of the complex task of defining an input file type with enough precision to guarantee its successful processing by a workflow or tool.
- Chapter 5: Tools and tool registries - ranging from code repositories through deployable packages to pre-deployed tools already available in computational or workflow platforms, and a review of repositories for code and applications.
- Chapter 6: The problem of building reliable machine-actionable methods for the retrieval of file metadata and the file objects themselves from a wide diversity of research data repositories.
- Chapter 7: The challenge of describing and inventorying deployment and execution platforms that can include anything from local machines to network servers, VREs, cloud platforms, HPC, and dedicated workflow execution resources.

An information model is derived to describe the definitions and interrelationships between the actors, concepts, and objects that are in scope for these topics, and the

recommendations define the next steps required for implementation by work packages and participating repositories in the EOSC Data Commons project. This is presented in Chapter 8.

1. Introduction

The landscape analysis presented in this report deals with the aspects of matching datasets with appropriate tools and execution platforms, and packaging this information in such a way that it can be presented to user-selected platforms for execution. In this process, the broad-based user expectations are, as defined in the DoA, the following:

1. A **Metadata Catalogue**, which will be developed in WP4 of the EOSC Data Commons project, implements a mechanism whereby datasets can be linked to appropriate tools.
2. In principle, any metadata catalogue that implements the relevant interoperability specifications can accomplish the same.
3. The tools can be matched with datasets² in two ways:
 - a. Directly (or 'deterministically', as described in the DoA), which implies that datasets are linked to applicable tools on the basis of **typing**. For this to work well, typing has to be precise, and matches are near-guaranteed to be workable.
 - b. Indirectly (or 'probabilistically'), by identifying possible good matches between datasets and types through **machine learning**. This matching process will not always result in a feasible combination, and should be viewed as recommendations. Using this method, an algorithm can impute or guess the type of the dataset based on training data of known matches.
4. Types have to be defined unambiguously, irrespective of the method followed to identify them, and this implies the existence of a **Type Registry**, which can be used to reliably describe and reference types at varying levels of detail and granularity. The types are not trivial to describe properly, as we will see in the detailed sections later on.
5. The datasets, once a type is explicitly determined or imputed, can be matched with instances of tools maintained and curated in a **Catalogue of Tools**.
6. The tools themselves are deployable on a variety of platforms, ranging from tools that are very flexible (for example, will run on any platform, or have modest requirements in terms of storage, computing capacity, memory, and operating system), to tools that are developed and implemented on only one platform and will only run there (for example, some research workflows) or have significant resource demands. Another class of tool is available only operationally, can only be accessed on a specific production platform, and the code cannot be deployed elsewhere. These characteristics of platforms and the types of tools they allow are important to define as a pathway to specification of metadata for platforms.
7. In principle, tools and platforms have a many-to-many relationship, and there should be a **Registry of Platforms**. In practice, it is thought that such a registry will be quite difficult to implement, and it may be more practical to rely on two complementary mechanisms: allowing platforms to self-advertise the tools and tool 'families' that they are capable of supporting, and harvesting this information to the Catalogue of

² We develop these services in EOSC Data Commons for datasets, but any catalogue of research outputs that can be typed (software, semantic artefacts, publications) are in scope for similar implementations.

Tools. Some tools may be excluded from platforms on the basis of resource requirements (RAM, processors, storage capacity, GPUs) even though the tool 'family' is permissible. As an example, a platform may be capable of hosting any LLM, unless the GPU requirement exceeds a given value.

8. Assuming that an object (file) in a dataset can be matched successfully with at least one tool in the Catalogue of Tools, and that this combination is known to be deployable on at least one platform, the task that remains then involves the following, as performed by the **Request Packager**:
 - a. Obtaining metadata and a download or access link for the file, so that the deployment platform has all the information it needs to process the file. This aspect may lead to an additional filtering step, since platforms may have constraints in terms of allowable file size, as an example. This implies that generic limitations in respect of file characteristics ideally need to be included into platform metadata.
 - b. Information about the tool, its source (if not already deployed to the platform), and the file manifest and accompanying metadata need to be presented to a platform for deployment and execution in a **Package**.
9. The responsibilities of WP5 end when such a package has been compiled, requested for deployment, and made available (or not) on the requested platform. This implies an additional functionality - that of recording the state of a deployment request, and having a mechanism available for updating its state or being notified of a state change.
10. The above components are all part of the '**Matchmaker**' service in the EOSC Data Commons.

Landscape Analysis for the Packaging Specification and Components

Figure 1.1: High-Level (Context) Architecture³

WP6 is responsible for handling deployment requests, updating state (either through a push or pull mechanism), and running the request (code/ tool and data) once the package has been deployed. The components involved in this sequence of events form part of the **'Data Player'** service in EOSC Data Commons.

The high-level component architecture is shown in Figure 1.1, with the components to be developed by WP5 highlighted in green. (WP4 = blue, and WP6 = orange).

³ High resolution version: <https://s.icepanel.io/FxtyLAp7hKzqxX/YvJw>

2. Methodology

2.1. Desktop Study

The information presented in this report is based largely on a desktop study of the relevant topics, supplemented by inputs from project participants. The focus of the desktop study was the scope, applicable standards and specifications, and working implementations applicable to four interrelated topics:

1. Describing, unambiguously referencing, and inventorising the types associated with research data objects, with a view to linking them to tools, applications, and workflows (“Tools”) that can accept these types of data as inputs;
2. Describing, referencing, and inventorising tools that are of interest and use to researchers; and
3. Describing and identifying the platforms to which tools and data can be deployed for processing.
4. Designing and describing the dataset(s) or file(s), tool(s), and target platform for deployment in a package.

In evaluating materials reviewed for the desktop study, the intention of developing a Catalogue of Tools, supplemented by Type and Platform registries determined the selection and assessment of relevant implementations, standards, and specifications. Throughout, the objective to avoid duplication by implementing harmonising ‘facade’ applications for existing services was kept in mind.

2.2. Use Case Contributions

Use case contributions to the content of the registries will be a task to follow the publication of this report. It was, however, possible to start already with harvesting file types from repositories participating in the Proof-of-Concept to construct a first inventory of the Type Registry. These repositories included KNAW-DANS (5 repositories), DABAR, HAL, and SWISSUbase. This effort also provided practical feedback on the likely diversity of machine-actionable access to file metadata in different repositories that could be translated into design considerations for future refinement.

2.3. Liaison with Other HE Projects

There are ongoing HE projects that will be able to provide additional inputs, and also feedback on the specification and Proof-of-Concept outputs that will follow in September and November 2025. The most prominent of these is the EOSC EDEN project, which is currently working on package specifications for exchange between repositories and their supporting services, and should be viewed as an expert input to our package specifications.

2.4. Derivation of Information Models

In the desktop study, we also reviewed material that could be useful⁴ in derivation of information models - definition of the objects, actors, and concepts that form part of our scope of work. Such standards and specifications are important for developing a linked open data based (and therefore AI-ready) registry of Tools, Types, and Platforms.

⁴ For example the DCAT-AP model proposed for EOSC

3. Exchange Packages

There are several broad families of metadata and/ or data exchange package formats and specifications, each focused on a community and type of use that benefits from its standardisation in specific research object life cycle stages. This chapter examines each of these broad application areas in more detail, and a summary is provided at the conclusion of the chapter.

3.1. Trustworthy Repositories

Trustworthy repositories are largely directed in respect of their activities, procedures, and standards by the Open Archival Information Services Reference Model [1], [6] (OAIS-RM), which has been available as a framework for more than 2 decades. Originally developed for management of space-based observation data by the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS), it has been widely adopted in the digital library and archive ecosystem, and forms the basis of the certification of trustworthy repositories via authorities such as the CoreTrustSeal [2] and ISO 14721 [4]. It can also be used to informally verify alignment using TRAC [3].

OAIS-RM is a conceptual model or framework, and does not specify any standards for implementation.

3.1.1. SIP, DIP, and AIP

A central premise of the OAIS-RM is the definition of three 'packages' of content that are of interest to digital archives, and each serves a different purpose. These are:

- **Submission Information Package (SIP):** Package sent by the Producer (data depositor) to the Archive.
- **Archival Information Package (AIP):** Package stored and preserved within the OAIS Archive.
- **Dissemination Information Package (DIP):** Package delivered by the Archive to a Consumer in response to an access request.

Each of these are different in respect of the objects and metadata contained in the package. As an example, the formats of digital objects submitted by a depositor may not be based on any preferences except in respect of the working environment of the researcher or the tools available to them. For dissemination purposes, most communities and domains have clear preferences and conventions (such as which file formats and vocabularies to use), while long-term preservation of objects has a completely different perspective - that of maximising future readability by humans and machines, and decoupling from any proprietary standards or software associated with a format.

3.1.2. Standards for OAIS-RM implementation

The OAIS-RM concepts find expression in guidelines, standards for implementation, and serialisation specifications in a set of related bodies of work:

- PREMIS (Preservation Metadata Implementation Strategies) [5], [8] which is widely supported and adapted in the preservation landscape, and is influential due to its development by the US Library of Congress. PREMIS provides guidelines for implementation of preservation metadata: in other words, the scope of metadata to be included into AIPs.
- METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard) [9] is a standard aimed at package metadata, and can be used as a basis for implementation of SIP, DIP, and AIP metadata.
- XFDU [7] was developed independently by the CCSDS as a basis for implementation of OAIS-RM, and it is less widely adopted even though it is endorsed by ISO. It finds use mostly in space missions.

3.2. BagIt and its derivations, SWORD Protocol

The BagIt standard was developed by the US Library of Congress and the California Digital Library in 2002, and adopted formally in 2007 ([IETF RFC 8493](https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc8493/)⁵) [10] and is commonly used for content and checksum transport, extended with a metadata section. It is a direct response to the need of archives and libraries to transfer large sets of digital files with built-in fixity checking and a manifest for verification, as simply as possible. It is a standard implementation in repository software platforms such as Dryad and Dataverse.

The original Library of Congress specification has subsequently been extended to include profiling [11], and as such, is highly flexible in its implementation. RO-Crate (see below) is compatible with and can be integrated with BagIt in various ways⁶.

BagIt packages are frequently deposited via the SWORD protocol [12], and is widely adopted for automated submissions to archives. The SWORD Protocol, originally based on ATOM, has evolved over time, and is currently in its third release:

- SWORD 1.0 (2008) [12]: A protocol (based on AtomPub) to allow automated deposit into repositories (esp. institutional repositories).
- SWORD 2.0 (2012) [13]: Expanded to support multiple files, multipart packages, updates, and replace/append operations.
- SWORD 3.0 (2020 draft, ongoing [14]): Refocuses around modern REST patterns and JSON representations.

SWORD is extremely useful, since it supports a variety of actions, as well as authentication, in a standardised way. DANS, for example, has implemented a BagIt profile and a SWORD 2.0 implementation, and it receives thousands of automated submissions annually to its repositories and long-term preservation service using this approach [15]. Table 3.2.1 provides a summary of example SWORD Implementations.

⁵ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc8493/>

⁶ There are some caveats as the recipient of the package must be aware of what layout was used to compose them, and graceful degradation is possible to only one of the formats.

Table 3.2.1 Notable SWORD Implementations

Repository / Service	SWORD Support	Notes
Harvard Dataverse ⁷	Yes (SWORD 2.0)	Dataset deposits, API-based ingest.
Software Heritage ⁸	Yes (SWORD 2.0)	Source code archiving.
DSpace ⁹	Yes (SWORD 1.0/2.0)	Widespread institutional repository support.
EPrints ¹⁰	Yes (SWORD 1.0/2.0)	Plugin-based, automated deposits.
Fedora Commons / Islandora ¹¹	Yes (via add-ons)	Used in Fedora-based ecosystems.
CKAN ¹²	Partial / experimental	Research data portals.
PresQT	Experimental	Crosswalks to multiple repositories.

In addition to the list in Table 3.2.1, [PresQT](#)¹³ has tested the SWORD interfaces to sizable number of repository targets, including OSF, curateND, GitHub, Zenodo (by implication including Invenio/ B2SHARE), GitLab, and FigShare, and it has tested which source (export) BagIt packages can be successfully submitted to the SWORD interfaces of other repository targets. The interoperability results are quite satisfactory [16], indicating that the SWORD protocol and the BagIt specification (or its derivatives) for payloads can serve as a basis for interoperable package exchange.

3.3. RO-Crate

BagIt is firmly focused on exchange of content in a reliable way, and through the SWORD protocol, it takes care of syntactic and schematic interoperability. It is, however, completely agnostic in respect of the content it transports, and RO-Crate fills this need by providing semantic linking [17].

RO-Crate is a community-driven specification for packaging research data, software, and workflows along with rich metadata in a machine-actionable, FAIR-compliant way [18]. It is based on JSON-LD, which describes the contents of a digital research object, its context, and relationships. A minimal RO-Crate is just a single file (ro-crate-metadata.json) plus a README, but typically includes references to files (data, code, and workflow descriptions) and linked objects (instruments, protocols, etc.).

⁷ <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/sword.html>

⁸ <https://docs.softwareheritage.org/devel/swh-deposit/specs/protocol-reference.html>

⁹ <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSDOC6x/SWORD>

¹⁰ <http://wiki.eprints.org/w/SWORD>

¹¹ <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/FEDORA38/SWORD>

¹² <https://ckan.org/>

¹³ <https://presqt.readthedocs.io/>

The specification is actively being developed (by [Research Objects](https://www.researchobject.org/)¹⁴) and originates from the needs of the UK and EU Life Sciences research community, funded by projects such as [Wf4Ever](http://wf4ever.github.io/ro/)¹⁵ and [BioSchemas](http://bioschemas.org/)¹⁶.

RO-Crate is in increasing use, and is endorsed and extended by a variety of projects, infrastructures, and initiatives, including ELIXIR, WorkflowHub, RO-Hub, Zenodo, ARDC, and EOSC.

RO-Crate is useful for describing the relationships between actors and objects involved in a research context, and includes semantic relations between research datasets and files, software and workflows, people, organisations, provenance, citations, and other identifiers. It is capable of describing additional context such as instruments, protocols, and methodologies, and is one of the primary mechanisms for supporting provenance records of computational research workflows, and to enable reproducibility. It is designed to be interoperable with schema.org¹⁷ and is based on JSON-LD encoding.

RO-Crate has some shortcomings in respect of typical archive requirements, since it does not explicitly store checksums or ensure bit-level integrity, it defines the metadata model and directory layout, not how crates are exchanged or stored, and unlike PREMIS or METS, it does not model digital preservation events, rights, or long-term management explicitly. Since RO-Crate can be profiled and extended to suit any need, the hybrid approaches discussed later are well-suited to addressing these requirements.

3.4. Signposting and FAIR Digital Objects

Signposting and FAIR Digital Objects are two approaches that have the same objective in mind: reducing the friction for machines in finding actionable metadata and data, thereby improving FAIRness [20].

FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) have evolved from an early, rigid interpretation [19] that required significant adjustments to existing standards, and development of new standards to support their implementation¹⁸. As such, it presented a practical limitation irrespective of the quality of the original concept [21] (which predates the FAIR principles, and gave rise to the Handle System). The FDO concept was developed in about 2018, focused on the emerging EOSC, and aiming to make digital objects self-describing, actionable, and interoperable in line with FAIR principles.

Current approaches are far more pragmatic, and the FDO Forum summarised the recent flexibility of implementation approach in a white paper [22].

¹⁴ <https://www.researchobject.org/>

¹⁵ <http://wf4ever.github.io/ro/>

¹⁶ <http://bioschemas.org/>

¹⁷ <http://schema.org>

¹⁸ Early definitions emphasised a need for standardised types, a new or dedicated fdo:// protocol, and tight coupling to specific identifier systems (e.g., Handle/DOI), and elicited significant community pushback.

These changes make it compatible with Signposting [23], which follows a different approach, and is based on existing open standards and vocabularies. Signposting includes machine-actionable links in the HEAD response of an HTTP request, or alternatively points from the HEAD request to a Linkset file¹⁹ location. The Linkset file uses a JSON-LD syntax to encode information about related resources.

There are two main practical differences between FDO implementations and Signposting [24], [25]:

- The first concerns where first access to a resource is expected. FDO implementations assume that the first contact will be via PID resolution, and that resolvers need to direct machines as efficiently as possible to resource-related information ('PID-centric'). Signposting assumes that first contact will be via web crawlers or links on web pages, and that the machines need to be efficiently directed based on an attempt to process an HTTP request to a resource ('web-centric'). Both of these use cases occur all the time, and it is not possible to select a preferred approach.
- The second difference lies in the locus of authority, and here Signposting has a clear advantage. For most resources, the authoritative version of metadata ('custom' metadata) is maintained locally by the repository, and synchronised from time to time with 'kernel' metadata maintained by the PID provider. Some FDO options go even further, requiring the metadata to be captured as part of the 'identifier' metadata at the resolver registry. Both kernel metadata and identifier metadata are prone to synchronisation lags, and may not be able to express the full extent of the custom metadata schema, leading to out-of-date or lossy metadata records [25].

Either way, a hybrid approach that allows either PID-centric or web-centric entry points, but directs machines immediately to the most authoritative and up-to-date actionable information would clearly be the most practical implementation.

The significance of these approaches to packaging lies in automated creation of such packages: given a PID or an HTTP address to a dataset landing page, one should be able to automatically construct a BagIt, SIP, or RO-Crate package for that object, leading to a high degree of interoperability and flexibility. These packages can be supplemented with tool matches to serve as the basis for a deployment request.

3.5. Hybrid Approaches

BagIt and RO-Crate are complementary (BagIt provides bitstream packaging, validation, and fixity checking, and RO-Crate provides semantic metadata and contextual description), and as such, either one of the following two hybridisations are possible:

¹⁹ The links can also be included in the <head> tag of the HTML page, but this requires larger downloads than a HEAD request. Also available from a GET request in the HTTP Link header.

- RO-Crate manifests can be placed inside a BagIt payload (RO-Crate provides metadata; BagIt provides transport/integrity). One such option is referred to as 'BigBag' [26,] previously referred to as BagIt-RO.
- RO-Crate can be extended with a BagIt profile (RO-Crate in /data, metadata in BagIt manifests).

We will revisit the BagIt and RO-Crate hybrid options when discussing file metadata in Chapter 6.

3.6. Summary of Approaches

Table 3.6.1 summarises the scope and applicable standards from an OAIS-RM perspective.

Table 3.6.1: Scope and Implementation Options for OAIS-RM Packages

OAIS Package Type	Conceptual Scope	Core Characteristics	Typical Implementations / Specifications
Submission Information Package (SIP)	Package sent by the Producer (data depositor) to the Archive.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contains Content Information (data object + representation information) and Packaging Information. - May contain Preservation Description Information (PDI), but completeness is not required. - Form and granularity defined by submission agreement / ingest workflow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> METS (Metadata Encoding & Transmission Standard, ISO 28500) commonly used for packaging SIPs. - BagIt (IETF RFC 8493) widely adopted for content + checksum transport. - OAI-ORE (Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse & Exchange) for describing aggregations. - Community SIP profiles: e.g., DataCite Submission packages, EUDAT B2SAFE SIP profile.
Archival Information Package (AIP)	Package stored and preserved within the OAIS Archive.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Must include Content Information + full PDI (Preservation Description Information). - Managed by the archive for long-term preservation. - Includes Packaging Information and Descriptive Information (to support finding/using AIP). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAIS AIP conceptually informs METS, PREMIS, and OAIS-compliant repository implementations (e.g., Fedora, Archivematica, Rosetta). - PREMIS (Preservation Metadata, ISO 28500 extension) widely used for PDI. - METS used as structural wrapper for AIP (content + metadata). - XFDU (XML Formatted Data Unit, CCSDS 651.0-B-2) explicitly designed as a serialization of OAIS AIP/ SIP.
Dissemination Information Package (DIP)	Package delivered by the Archive to a Consumer in response to an access request.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Derived from one or more AIPs.- Contains the requested Content Information and enough PDI to understand/use it. - May be simpler/flattened compared to AIP. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DIPs often implemented using METS profiles (delivery packages with descriptive + structural metadata). - BagIt used for delivery (esp. for datasets, e.g., Dryad, Dataverse exports). - OAI-PMH or ResourceSync for DIP

		- Optimized for access, not preservation.	dissemination in repositories. - No single mandatory standard; depends on access platform and community conventions.
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Table 3.6.2 provides a comparison between RO-Crate, BagIt, and METS in respect of metadata approaches and possibilities.

Table 3.6.2: Comparison Between RO-Crate, BagIt, and METS

Aspect	RO-Crate	BagIt	METS
Origin / Governance	Research Object community BioSchema, supported by EOSC, ELIXIR, ARDC	Library of Congress (2007) California Digital Library (2007) Standardized by IETF as RFC 8493 (2018)	Library of Congress maintained by METS Editorial Board
Primary Purpose	FAIR, machine-actionable metadata packaging of research data, software, workflows	Reliable file packaging & transfer with checksums for integrity	Structural wrapper for digital objects binding content files with descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata
Core Representation	JSON-LD (ro-crate-metadata.json) schema.org aligned	Simple text manifests (bagit.txt, manifest-*.txt) Payload in /data	XML schema (METS document) referencing content files and metadata
Strengths	FAIR metadata JSON-LD / Linked Data ready Lightweight & human-readable Integrates datasets, workflows, people, citations	Simple and robust Checksums/ fixity validation Widely adopted for exchange Standardised (RFC 8493)	Rich preservation metadata support Flexible structuring of multiple metadata schemas (e.g., PREMIS) Strong community profiles in cultural heritage and digital preservation
Limitations	No built-in fixity or transfer validation Not designed for long-term preservation metadata	Minimal semantics (no rich metadata) No preservation or descriptive context	XML-heavy, relatively complex Harder to implement for lightweight workflows Less aligned with Linked Data/FAIR principles
OAIS Role	Often used for SIP (submission with rich metadata) Emerging use for DIP (data delivery with FAIR context)	Common for SIP and DIP (exchange & delivery) Less common for AIP (storage)	Commonly used for AIP (archival storage) and SIP in preservation workflows
Compatibility	Can be embedded within BagIt (BagIt provides transport + fixity; RO-Crate	Can carry RO-Crate metadata inside /data folder	Can embed PREMIS metadata for preservation events

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	provides metadata) Can be cross-walked into METS for preservation contexts	Can carry METS or PREMIS documents inside the payload	Can incorporate identifiers to RO-Crate or BagIt packages as content
Typical Use Cases	WorkflowHub FAIRDOM-SEEK DataPLANT EOSC research data workflows	Library of Congress transfers Dryad/Dataverse exports APTrust Chronopolis	Digital preservation repositories (Fedora, Archivematica, Rosetta, national libraries/archives)

Based on the discussion in this chapter, we make recommendations on package specifications and exchange for EOSC Data Commons in Chapter 8.

4. Types and Type Registries

The internet has relied on media type definitions almost from the start, as defined and maintained by [IANA](https://iana.org/)²⁰ (Internet Assigned Numbers Authority) [27] based on a publicly accessible process [56] (anyone can request a new media type to be registered by IANA).

4.1. Type Definitions

Type definitions, and especially type definitions of files, are based first and foremost on a file extension (which may already determine the schema, structure, and sometimes the semantics of the content). Considering text files as an example, one can have many variations of such text files: it can, for instance, be an unstructured text file (.txt), a comma-delimited file (.csv), an XML file (.xml), or an HTML file (.html).

4.1.1. IANA MIME Types

These differences in structuring of a file, and the rules that determine whether it is structurally valid, are primarily referenced using an [IANA MIME Type](https://iana.org/)²¹. These MIME types, in turn, reference an information sheet and a specification of the structure, and possibly semantics, associated with such a file. Using XML files as an example, one can determine from IANA that such files have W3C specification governance, and a MIME Type specification based on RFC 7303²².

4.1.2. Schemas and Profiles

Continuing with the XML text file example, it is a common occurrence to have many standardised variations of XML, as exemplified by a long list of metadata schemas expressed in XML based on a schema definition (XSD). To distinguish one schema from another, it is imperative to specify the schema in addition to the MIME Type - it matters greatly to consuming applications whether the schema is aligned to its expectations.

In many cases, the schema does not adequately represent context related to a jurisdiction, community, domain, or institution. This is addressed by developing profiles of the schema, and such profiles can be more specific and restrictive than the schema. It can, for example, prescribe a localised vocabulary instead of a general one, and make some elements mandatory instead of optional. The salient point is that some consuming applications will fail if the input file is not profile-compliant.

4.1.3. Graph-Like Relationships

An additional characteristic of MIME type, schemas, and profiles concerns the relationship between them. MIME types, profiles, and schemas are related in two generic ways:

1. Some files are specialisations of others. In our examples, an XML file and a CSV file are both text files, and any tool or process that is capable of processing a text file should be able to accept either as input. Similarly, both HTML-4 files and XML files

²⁰ <https://iana.org/>

²¹ https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Guides/MIME_types

²² <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc7303.html>

can be accepted by processes requiring valid XML as input. The same applies to schemas and profiles of these files.

2. Some files are related and based on the same basic encoding, for example JSON files are all text files, even though the MIME type for JSON files are not explicitly linked to text files.

Figure 4.1.3.1: Illustration of the MIME Type Graph - Text Example²³

Detecting these relationships in MIME types based on the underlying organisation and schema for MIME Type formulation is not feasible, since it will only identify some relationships and miss others. Any algorithm developed for analysis of MIME type structures will identify many, but not all, of generic type 1, and probably only a few of generic type 2.

These relationships are conceptually a graph, and many of the relationships between MIME types, schemas, and profiles will have to be manually curated to be useful and applicable.

4.1.4. Composite and Complex Types, Type Registries

There are resources available that can be used to describe file objects in more detail, for example by using the Data Type Registry (DTR²⁴) developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC or one operated by CNRI²⁵. The basic premise here would be that one could define a set of types and composites of those types, starting with foundational types such as text, date/time, boolean, etc., and then progressively define schema from this basis. We consider such additional granularity as useful, but given the scope of the EOSC Data Commons (successfully linking file objects to processing tools and processes), we will not investigate in detail how type registries can be used to improve the granularity of description of such objects.

²³ High-resolution version:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1w2VBkP1S3e5e0-67-zwAHYTvF8tbVKMw5CithSMob08>

²⁴ <https://typeregistry.pidconsortium.net/#urls/objects/design?payload=home>

²⁵ <https://typeregistry.org/>

4.2. Type Registries

We examine both general-purpose and domain-specific type registries.

4.2.1. General Types

Even though IANA serves as a custodian of MIME types, they do not offer an authoritative API service that allows listing, identification, and detailed description of MIME types. This is a prerequisite for using MIME types and their schema or profile specialisations as nodes in a graph, and using them as Linked Open Data references in metadata or other resources, as we intend to do in the EOSC Data Commons project.

The need can be addressed in more than one way, including:

- **Data Type Registry:** A secondary application of type registries such as the DTR²⁶ would be the registration of types (especially types that include schemas and profiles) in a publicly available type registry that offers mechanisms for curation and maintenance. The DTR occasionally harvests and updates all MIME types from IANA, and as such, it can be used as a basis for an authoritative type registry. The DTR has some advantages in this role, including the ability to add custom properties (which EOSC Data Commons would want to do), and the ability to define relations between types (required to construct the graph of relationships between types). A disadvantage would be the reliance on a third-party infrastructure of which the future availability is uncertain.
- **IANA-Based:** One can process IANA MIME Type downloads²⁷ or services that parse and process such downloads, for example the MIME DB²⁸ project that offers GitHub-based resources for developers to use. This would require additional layers of complexity to address the following two cases:
 - Registering new types is a public process [56] and will not necessarily be successful. The MIME Type structure also does not explicitly allow for the definition of all schema and profile specialisations.
 - There is no provision for registration of additional properties and relations between MIME Types in the basic structure offered by IANA or MIME DB.

In addition to IANA-based information, there are two additional resources that are of importance in respect of file type information and referencing:

- **WikiData:** [WikiData](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page)²⁹ contains structured and linked data on a large number of file formats, and as such, is a significant resource and potential source of default URIs for these formats. WikiData can serve as an automated curation tool, since it can be used to link file types to MIME types, obtain metadata in respect of file type specifications and authorities, other URIs that may exist, and (sometimes) related types.

²⁶ <https://typeregistry.pidconsortium.net/#objects/21.11104/87efe6353f9d42f690e3>

²⁷ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

²⁸ <https://github.com/jshttp/mime-db>

²⁹ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

- **PRONOM** [74]: [PRONOM](https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/)³⁰ is a technical registry of file formats and related software products, maintained by The National Archives (UK) [75], and widely used in the digital library and archive/ repository ecosystem. It describes file format signatures, encodings, software, and dependencies. It is the authoritative basis for the [DROID](https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/preserving-digital-records/droid/)³¹ tool (Digital Record Object Identification, [74]), which automates file format verification in preservation workflows. Each file format is assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID). PRONOM has several extremely useful services, including
 - [PRONOM XML export](https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/exportingdata.htm)³² (all file formats in XML).
 - Individual format view³³ (HTML or XML per PUID).
 - DROID signature files: downloadable from The National Archives, used by DROID for local identification. This is a very useful service for verifying file type, which is prudent prior to transfer of large files or running computationally expensive workflows, and can be used to determine computationally equivalent MIME types.

The MIME DB resources are attractive from a number of perspectives, including the harvesting of types from more than one source (IANA, Apache, and NGINX). It will, as a result, contain types that for whatever reason cannot or have not yet been registered with IANA. MIME DB also offers open source code that can be adapted or forked to serve as a basis of EOSC Data Commons Type Registry development, as applicable. This can be supplemented by and harmonised with metadata extraction from WikiData and with the file type inventory curated by PRONOM.

4.2.2. Domain-Specific Type Registries and Types

There are a number of prominent domain-specific type registries, and special types are common in most domains. The life sciences, through EDAM [57], are particularly active in this regard, since many analysis or workflow outcomes produce specialised files tailored to the content. The earth and environmental sciences domain provides another example (in this case format-specific, and not necessarily used only in the domain) where spatially referenced data is supported by a sizable number of standardised and commonly used formats.

EDAM (EMBRACE Data And Methods) is a domain ontology for bioinformatics concepts, and is a particularly well developed example. It contains stable definitions and URIs for a number of interrelated concepts

- Operations (e.g., sequence alignment)
- Data types (e.g., nucleotide sequence, phylogenetic tree)
- Identifiers (e.g., UniProt accession, DOI)
- Data formats (e.g., FASTA, BAM, VCF)

³⁰ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/>

³¹

<https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/information-management/manage-information/preserving-digital-records/droid/>

³² <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/help/pronom/exportingdata.htm>

³³ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/fmt/18>

The “Data formats” branch of EDAM contains more than 400 items describing file formats commonly used in bioinformatics. Each format concept has URI identifiers, preferred labels, synonyms, and definitions. Critically, those synonyms include MIME Types, where applicable. [Appendix A](#) provides a subset of these as an example.

Table 4.2.2.1 lists a sample of important domain-specific type registries.

Table 4.2.2.1: A Sample of Domain-Specific Type Registries

Registry / Ontology	Domain	Explicit file format/type vocabulary?	Scope / Notes	Reference
EDAM	Bioinformatics	Yes “Data formats” branch	Covers operations, data, identifiers, and formats; widely used in bio.tools, WorkflowHub, Galaxy.	[64]
OBI (Ontology for Biomedical Investigations)	Biomedical research	No	Focuses on assays, protocols, materials; refers to data but not file format vocabularies.	[65]
ISA Model / ISA-Tab	Life sciences experiments	Indirectly (points to formats via metadata fields)	Captures metadata and links to experimental data files; does not itself define formats.	[66]
MIAME / MAGE-TAB	Microarray data	Yes defines standard file structures	Not an ontology, but a prescriptive “minimum information” checklist tied to file standards.	[67]
PSI (Proteomics Standards Initiative – PSI-MI, PSI-MS)	Proteomics	Yes standardizes exchange file formats (e.g., mzML, mzIdentML, mzTab)	Ontologies linked to community-defined XML/Tab formats; heavily used in proteomics tools.	[68]
CellML / SED-ML / SBML (COMBINE standards)	Systems biology	Yes XML schemas defining model and simulation files	Define machine-readable file formats for models (SBML, CellML) and simulation experiments (SED-ML).	[69]
NeuroML	Neuroscience	Yes XML-based model description format	Defines file format for neuronal models and network connectivity.	[70]
DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)	Social sciences	Metadata-focused, not file formats	Captures variable/metadata descriptions; refers to external formats (CSV, SAV, etc.) but does not define them.	[71]
CF Conventions (NetCDF Climate & Forecast)	Earth sciences	Yes defines conventions for NetCDF file contents	Not a general ontology but a specification of variables, units, structures inside NetCDF files.	[72]

DDI-CDI / RO-Crate	Cross-disciplinary	Focused on metadata packaging	Define cross-domain integration (DDI-CDI) and FAIR packaging (RO-Crate); refer to but don't enumerate file formats.	[73]
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4.3. Preferred File Formats

Preferred formats for archiving is a major consideration in the field of digital preservation. Many repositories publish guidance in respect of preferred file formats to assist depositors with submission preparation, and for specific domains, there is also general guidance available.

Table 4.3.1 provides a summary of the main services and guidance sources in this respect, and Appendix B provides additional detail on access to services and guidance, typical recommendations per file group, and supporting resources.

Table 4.3.1: Example Services for Preferred Format Guidance and API Services

Resource	Scope	Content	Notes
Library of Congress Sustainability of Digital Formats	Widely used global reference for audiovisual, images, text, datasets, 3D, GIS, etc.	Format descriptions, sustainability factors, MIME mappings, references.	Provides HTML pages; no public API, but some data is structured enough to scrape.
UK National Archives PRONOM	Technical registry of file formats, software, and signatures.	File families (text, image, AV, GIS, 3D). Links to MIME, PUIDs.	No REST API, but widely used in preservation tools (DROID, Siegfried).
NARA (US National Archives) Transfer & Preservation Guidelines	Preferred formats for official US federal records (text, still images, AV, GIS, 3D).	Explicit "acceptable" vs. "preferred" formats for long-term access.	No API.
Open Preservation Foundation (OPF) File Format Policies / Registries	Community-driven preservation best practices.	Hosts COPTR (Community Owned digital Preservation Tool Registry) which includes format guidance and links.	No API, but structured wiki.
European Commission EUDAT B2SHARE/ EOSC Guidance	Recommends file formats for FAIR data deposition across scientific domains.	Guidance lists preferred file types for tabular, geospatial, audiovisual, etc.	No dedicated API for file format guidance.

Dataverse Community/ File Handling and Formats	File families supported by Dataverse (tabular, GIS, audio, video, images).	Provides explicit support and recommendations (e.g., Shapefile, GeoTIFF, NetCDF for geospatial).	
Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) – Technology Watch & Guidance	High-level format family guidance for archives (text, AV, GIS, 3D).	Not a registry, but publishes format-focused Technology Watch Reports.	No API.
FITS (File Information Tool Set)/ JHOVE	Format identification and validation (esp. for archives).	Encodes preferred/preservation formats into validation rules.	No registry API; runs locally to identify file types.
PLANETS/ SCAPE / Archivemata policies	Preservation planning tools with configurable “format policies.”	Define preferred/acceptable formats at institutional level, often exported/sharable.	Provides JSON endpoints.
Harvard Library File Format Guidelines	Practical guidance across AV, text, images, GIS.		No API.
KNAW-DANS	Recommended file formats for specific file groups and domains, covering dissemination and long-term preservation considerations	Guidance documentation supported by an API	API

The implication is that type registries might be profiled by repositories and archives to indicate preferences determined by dissemination considerations (including links to tools), and by long-term preservation considerations. Effectively, formats that are linked to tools should become a de facto recommendation in respect of dissemination formats.

4.4. Definition of A Type Registry Facade

These considerations are all contributors to the design of a feasible Type Registry solution for EOSC Data Commons, and our preference is to regard this as a facade for existing services, coupled to selective harvesting and harmonisation of domain type registries. Such a facade, described in more detail in Chapter 8, can combine the positive aspects of resources such as the DTR and MIME DB, while allowing the extensibility, graph characteristics, and immediate update/ create/ delete responses required by EOSC Data Commons applications. It is also clear that the diversity and complexity of domain-specific file types, which are more directly useful to the research community, will require a significant

curation effort to harmonise and standardise the currently divergent approaches that have been reviewed in this chapter.

5. Tools and Tool Registries

End users add value to datasets and other research outputs using a variety of applications and workflows, and these are deployed and used in a variety of ways. The applications, workflows, and underlying code are collectively referred to in this context as ‘tools’, even though one could of course argue that it has a narrower meaning.

5.1. Definition of Value Addition

Value addition to research outputs [28] (datasets, code, semantic artefacts, scholarly publications) is a major objective of Open Science, and one of the imputed benefits of FAIR data [20], where reusability is one of the neglected focus areas.

In the EOSC Data Commons project, a specific objective is the development of mechanisms whereby ‘tools’ and datasets can be efficiently matched and deployed on behalf of end users, thereby stimulating reuse and removing barriers to such reuse.

Value addition resources can be deployed in different ways, including

- Locally, on the end user’s machine,
- In a VRE, which can be a generic environment offered to researchers by national cyberinfrastructure providers or commercial cloud environments, or
- In a High-Performance Computing (HPC) environment, typically also provisioned and offered by national research e-infrastructure providers, or
- In an Infrastructure as Service (IaaS) cloud offered by a research institution or a public cloud provider.

The type of deployment can be **on demand** (in other words, code and resources are made available and provisioned when requested), or **prepared**, for example by submitting datasets, configuration, and/ or code to an operational service or application running on the web or in a cloud environment.

The platform used for deployment can also be one of a number of options: for example running code and processing data in a local IDE environment or in local instances of applications; mobilising code, data, and other resources in a container, and deploying the containers locally, in a VRE, in the cloud, accessing workflows to process data and include custom code, and so on. Table 5.1.1 summarises these platform options, together with a high-level assessment of the typical advantages and disadvantages of each.

Table 5.1.1: Typical Platforms for Deployment of Data and Code

Option	Typical Use	Advantages	Disadvantages
Local (desktop/ IDE/ notebook)	Prototyping, small-scale analysis	Easy, fast	Limited resources
Containers (Docker/ Singularity)	Reproducibility, sharing	Portable, consistent	Setup overhead

Cloud (Research ³⁴ , AWS, etc.)	Scalable, on-demand	Flexible resources	Cost, internet needed
Remote server/ VM	Institutional compute	More resources	Administrative effort
HPC cluster	Large-scale, parallel jobs	High performance	Steep learning curve
VRE / Science gateway	Collaborative, domain-specific	User-friendly	Less flexible
Workflow systems	Complex, multi-environment pipelines	Reproducible	Higher setup cost

A special case involves Jupyter Notebook, which offers a standardised environment for interactive computing in a local, server, or web-based environment.

Work Package 6 in the EOSC Data Commons addresses the complexity of the alternatives available to end users for deployment of code and data, and to what extent it can be standardised. We do, however, need to understand the typology of these deployments as a means of indexing a Tool Registry, since not all types of deployment can be accommodated on all platforms. With that in mind, Work Package 5 will develop and implement a platform and deployment typology, based on the above as a vocabulary for the metadata associated with tools and platforms.

5.2. Code Repositories and Archives

5.2.1. Git-Based Repositories

The use of code repositories, such as GitHub, GitLab, or Bitbucket are pervasive in the research coding community, and unlikely to change in the foreseeable future. These repositories provide a reliable and consistent source of deployable code that is version-managed and unit-tested, and contribute significantly to development quality. Deployment of code happens almost exclusively from these repositories, whether the code is manually, automatically, or continuously deployed.

Git-based repositories have largely replaced other alternatives (Subversion, Mercurial) [29] and have significant advantages (distributed, collaborative, comprehensive, reliable, and supportive of branching and merging).

It is therefore clear that the most common source of code for deployment will be Git-based repositories, and that (1) their standard metadata is of interest to us, and (2) mechanisms for identifying and accessing code for deployment can be standardised based on the APIs offered by these repositories.

In terms of market share, GitHub is a clear leader, with 50-80% of users expressing this preference, followed by GitLab (between 10 and 40%), and Bitbucket (between 10 and 30%) [30], [31], [32], [33], [34]. The differences depend largely on whether end users are private (which may include many researchers) or corporate. GitHub is favoured by individual users, and less so by corporate users. In addition, GitLab software is open-source, while GitHub

³⁴ As supplied or brokered by national research cyberinfrastructure providers

isn't, this causes many research institutions to set up their own GitLab instances. From this we can conclude that GitHub and GitLab should be a primary focus as a source of research software and code, and that its integration should be prioritised.

5.2.2. Archiving Research Software and Code

Code repositories are highly flexible, allow branching, versioning, and merging, but this has a downside - long-term fixity. Fine-grained versioning is available and will reliably lead to an exact version of the code in the short term, but this reliability is not guaranteed for the long term. For research reproducibility and citability motivations, such long-term availability and fixity are important considerations.

There is a growing practice of archiving research code in Zenodo (more than 180,000 deposits at the time of writing³⁵) for the purposes of preservation (which is however not guaranteed by Zenodo), and more importantly, citability (which is instantly available via a DOI). These requirements are partly satisfied by Zenodo, and its visibility and ease of use are likely to strengthen this trend in the future.

Depositing code to Zenodo has an important additional downside: code is not directly deployable from there, and providing a reference to the version in a Git repository where deployment can be initiated is not a mandatory requirement, although it can be provided in a machine-actionable way as a related resource.

[Software Heritage](#)³⁶, in contrast, aims to provide long-term preservation of research code, and issues intrinsic identifiers [35] at any desired level of granularity for code artefacts, ranging from modules to projects, while maintaining the links between these artefacts. Because it is designed for code, it provides functionality that Zenodo does not, in addition to reliable machine-actionable deployment of the code, and the long-term preservation benefit. It implements the CodeMeta standard [36] for code metadata, and has developed good practices in respect of production-ready code [37]. These may influence the metadata that is defined for description of tools and the maturity of the tools. Github also provides an archive programme³⁷.

5.3. Code Metadata

As indicated above, there is an existing standard for code metadata (CodeMeta [36]) that is growing in adoption in research communities, and is supported, for example, in GitHub with a view to improvement of documentation quality. It is, however, far from the only available option. Table 5.3.1 provides a comprehensive overview of the choices available in respect of metadata schema and approaches for code.

³⁵ https://zenodo.org/search?q=&f=resource_type%3Asoftware&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

³⁶ <https://www.softwareheritage.org/>

³⁷ <https://archiveprogram.github.com>

Table 5.3.1 Summary of Code Metadata Schema Options

Standard / Format	Scope & Purpose	Key Fields / Focus	Strengths	Limitations / Gaps	Adoption & Ecosystem
CodeMeta (JSON-LD)	Research software metadata crosswalk	Title, authors, version, license, repo, dependencies	Interoperability Bridges Schema.org, DataCite, DOAP; JSON-LD native GitHub integration	Still evolving Requires mapping for completeness	Used in FAIR/academic contexts, endorsed by FORCE11, RDA
Schema.org (SoftwareApplication), (SoftwareSourceCode)	Web indexing, discovery	Name, description, programming language, download URL	Backed by search engines Widely used for structured web data	Lacks research-specific fields (e.g., citation, provenance)	Very high adoption on the web
DOAP (Description of a Project, RDF/XML)	Open-source project metadata	Project name, description, developers, repo, release	RDF-based Good for linked data Supported in Apache projects	Aging vocabulary Little active development	Historically used in open-source communities
DataCite Metadata Schema (+ Software extensions)	Citation and persistent identifiers (DOIs)	Creator, contributor, version, related identifiers	Strong PID integration DOI-based citation	Focused on citation, less on technical/software attributes	Widely used in repositories (Zenodo, institutional)
Software Heritage (SWHID + Graph)	Archiving, provenance, intrinsic identifiers	Content hashes, origin, version graph	Robust long-term archival Verifiable identifiers SWHID-based citation	Not descriptive (no human-readable metadata)	Strong adoption in preservation and FAIR projects
SPDX (ISO/IEC 5962:2021)	Software supply chain, licensing, SBOM	Package metadata, licenses, file checksums, dependencies	Industry standard Detailed license metadata	Not designed for citation or research context	Strong in industry, compliance, SBOM initiatives
CFF (Citation File Format, YAML)	Lightweight software citation	Title, authors, version, DOI, license	Simple Human-readable GitHub/ Zenodo	Limited metadata scope (citation-focused)	Increasing adoption in research repos (esp. GitHub)

Standard / Format	Scope & Purpose	Key Fields / Focus	Strengths	Limitations / Gaps	Adoption & Ecosystem
CodeMeta (JSON-LD)	Research software metadata crosswalk	Title, authors, version, license, repo, dependencies	Interoperability Bridges Schema.org, DataCite, DOAP; JSON-LD native GitHub integration	Still evolving Requires mapping for completeness	Used in FAIR/academic contexts, endorsed by FORCE11, RDA
			integration		
OpenAIRE Guidelines for Software Metadata	Interoperability for EU repositories	Based on CodeMeta & Schema.org	Harmonises across repositories	Guidelines only, not standalone schema	Adopted in EOSC / FAIR projects
ECO (Essential Characteristics of Open Science Software)	Maturity & openness assessment	Openness, sustainability, usability	Adds quality/maturity lens	Still under development	FAIR-IMPACT, community pilots

Based on Table 5.3.1, we conclude the following:

- It should be a string recommendation for inclusion of code into the Catalogue of Tools that a CodeMeta file be present in the Git repository where it is hosted.
- The Catalogue of Tools will use an archived copy of that same code and its SWHID as a PID for reliable citation and preservation of the code instance. If a copy is not available in Software Heritage, but a CodeMeta file is available in the Git repository, such an archive copy can be made on behalf of the owner of the code³⁸.
- If a reference to a package definition exists (SPDX, etc.), this should be included into the metadata.

5.4. Package Installation Services and Applications

Not all tools are deployed from code repositories, especially if the tools are production versions of applications, and package services play a significant role in this respect. It is not common for such applications to be the direct result of research code development, but popular tools include compiled production versions, and for that reason, one needs to understand the landscape and determine how and if the available content should be harvested or made harvestable by the Catalogue of Tools.

There are quite a number of such package services, largely distributed along ecosystem lines - for example, dealing with Node.js-related Javascript applications, Python applications, Java applications, and so on. Table 5.4.1 presents a partial but reasonably comprehensive list of these ecosystems and associated package services.

³⁸ DANS and other partners have implemented this in the [FAIRCORE4EOSC project](#)

Table 5.4.1: Package Services

Ecosystem	Package Service Examples
C/C++	vcpkg, conan
Cross-language	Spack (HPC), Guix, Nix
Go	go get (module system)
Java	Maven, Gradle
JavaScript / Node.js	npm, yarn, pnpm
PHP	composer
Python	pip, conda (broader environment manager)
R	CRAN, Bioconductor
Ruby	gem (RubyGems)
Rust	cargo
System packages	apt (Debian/Ubuntu), dnf (Fedora), pacman (Arch), Homebrew (macOS/Linux)

The typical content of the packages deployed by these services focus on integrity of delivery and trust, and for that reason, the metadata contained in each package include checksum information for all the resources included into the package. The typical content of such packages covers the following:

- Name and version of the package.
- Description or summary of the contents of the package and the application.
- Author/ maintainer information.
- License information.
- Dependencies (with version constraints).
- Entry points / executables (e.g. CLI commands, library modules).
- Build instructions / environment requirements (less common).
- Distribution artifact references (wheels, tarballs, source repositories).

This clearly overlaps with code metadata. Fortunately, CodeMeta has developed a set of crosswalks [38], including crosswalks for many of the package managers listed above.

The package services also mostly offer API endpoints from which package information and package lists can be retrieved, and these can be used to unambiguously identify a package, and obtain its package information.

From this assessment of the landscape, our conclusion is that

- If a tool is registered with the Catalogue of Tools on the basis of being available from a package manager already, the package information can, in many cases, be automatically harvested and translated to CodeMeta, while retaining a link to the package manager source and preserving the package information.

- The identifier in this case is the package manager (as a namespace) together with the package label or UUID (identifier).

5.5. Tool and Workflow Registries

Many tools and/or workflow definitions that orchestrate one or more tools and are of interest to researchers are registered and encoded in workflow-supporting platforms, such as Galaxy and WorkflowHub. Some of these support workflow execution as well as description, while some are restricted to the inventorisation and description of workflows and associated tools.

Table 5.5.1 provides an overview of the major workflow platforms available to the research community, together with important characteristics.

In addition to the registration of tools directly in workflow platforms, there are also independent tool registries, of which Table 5.5.2 provides some examples. These tool registries may have some overlap with the content of workflow registries.

[RO-Hub](#)³⁹ [124] serves as a special case - it is not explicitly designed as a workflow repository that links data file types and tools, and will accept any valid RO-Crate file as an input. In practice, though, many of the entries in RO-Hub are records of data object creation for the purposes of reproducibility, and these records can be mined for associations between data file types and tools or code via the API [125].

The range of platforms that are available, and their characteristics, lead to a number of conclusions:

- Some platforms serve a dual purpose, or are explicitly designed for tools registration, and as such need to be harvested for tool instances and definitions (Galaxy Toolshed, bio.tools, Dockstore).
- The EDAM ontology [57] has a specific file type definition section. It extends MIME types with domain-specific types, and is used in bio.tools, WorkflowHub, and Galaxy.
- Galaxy, which is a prominent workflow definition and execution platform, has its own internal standard for data types, which needs to be reconciled with a MIME-type and/or EDAM-based standardisation in the Type Registry.
- A disappointingly large number of tool registries do not record the input and output file types associated with the tool, which we regard as a major deficiency. These tools cannot therefore be included into a tool-type matched graph without human curation (likely impossible, given the volume), crowd-sourced annotation (which will only be partly effective), or AI-based annotation. The latter will most likely require human moderation and verification in any event.
- Most workflow and reproducibility-focused platforms - Galaxy, WorkflowHub, and ROHub - will explicitly or implicitly link input dataset types to tool definitions, and this is likely to be the most productive target for initial harvesting.

³⁹ <https://www.rohub.org/>

Table 5.5.1 Workflow Platforms and Their Characteristics

Platform	Short description	Tools	Workflows	Records input file types	Executes workflows	Notable standards / interoperability	Workflow description formalism / standards	References
Galaxy	Web platform for accessible, reproducible analysis with shareable histories, tools and workflows.	Yes (ToolShed)	Yes	Yes via Galaxy datatypes and tool XML	Yes (native)	Galaxy XML TRS client RO-Crate export	Galaxy Workflow format (JSON/XML internal) DAG semantics Can export/import via CWL, Workflow RO-Crate	[39],[40],[41]
Workflow Hub	Community registry to publish, find, cite and launch workflows; hub across WMSs.	No (tools via links, e.g., bio.tools)	Yes	Yes extracts from Workflow RO-Crate (EDAM terms)	No (launches in Galaxy via TRS)	Workflow RO-Crate Bioschemas TRS	Registry only Ingests Workflow RO-Crate (which can encapsulate CWL, WDL, Nextflow, Snakemake, Galaxy)	[42], [43]
LEXIS	HPC/Cloud orchestration platform for workflows across European supercomputers.	Partial (HPC commands/containers)	Yes (Workflow templates)	Partial (datasets as inputs/outputs) (no ontology)	Yes	Airflow/Yorc/HEApp iRODS staging	Uses Yorc/HEAppE with DAG execution Internally based on Apache Airflow DAGs for orchestration	[51]
Dockstore	GA4GH registry for tools & workflows (CWL/WDL/Nextflow/Galaxy).	Yes	Yes	Partial Descriptors (CWL, WDL) may define file formats	No (uses Terra, DNAnexus, etc.)	GA4GH TRS Multi-WMS support	Registry supports multiple standards: CWL, WDL, Nextflow DSL, Galaxy Relies on GA4GH TRS	[44], [45], [46]
Nextflow Tower	Control plane for orchestrating/running Nextflow pipelines across	No	No (manages pipelines, not	No	Yes	Nextflow DSL Container integrations	Nextflow DSL (domain-specific language, DAG-based) Partial CWL compatibility via export tools	[47], [48]

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	infrastructures.		registry)					
Terra	Managed cloud environment for WDL/Cromwell workflows with workspace model.	No	Workspace-level (not global registry)	Partial WDL types/inputs	Yes	Imports from Dockstore; Cromwell/WES	WDL (Workflow Description Language); executed with Cromwell engine (DAG-based semantics)	[49], [50]
Snakemake	Popular WMS using Python-based "Snakefiles" (rules, inputs, outputs, environments).	No	No registry Code-based	Yes – rules declare explicit input/output file patterns	Yes	Supports CWL export; container/env integration; provenance logging	Snakefile (Python DSL) → DAG defined by input/output rules; can export CWL; provenance logs	[54]
Apache Airflow	General-purpose workflow orchestration using DAGs in Python; widely used in data engineering & science.	No	No registry DAGs as code	Partial DAG tasks define inputs/outputs Non-standardised file types	Yes	Integrates with Kubernetes, cloud backends; strong scheduling & monitoring	DAGs in Python; each task is a node; no BPEL, but DAG-based orchestration standard in data engineering	[55]
ROHub	Reproducibility-focused registry of RO-Crates	Yes Implicitly recorded	Possibly	Yes Implicitly recorded	No	API Documentation https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/	RO-Hub acts as a repository that leverages RO-Crate to help publish , discover , and archive richly annotated Research Objects (ROs).	[124], [125], [77]

Table 5.2.2: Examples of Tool Registries

Registry	Domain	Description	API	File Types	Reference
bio.tools	Life sciences / bioinformatics	ELIXIR-supported portal for discovering tools, databases, services. Curated with rich metadata (biotoolsSchema, EDAM ontology). FAIRsharing, Galaxy/WorkflowHub links	REST API https://bio.tools/api/tool/?format=json	Yes – via EDAM	[52], [53], [57]
OMICtools	Biomedical, bio-data analysis	Community-curated search engine cataloging ~18,500 tools/databases with user reviews, discussions, citations.	API not operational - site largely defunct since 2019 - archive only	No	[58]
Astrophysics Source Code Library (ASCL)	Astronomy / astrophysics	Free registry of research software used in astronomy. Provides citations, indexing via ADS and other scholarly services.	REST API https://ascl.net/code/json	No	[59]
SciCodes Consortium	Cross-disciplinary, initiated in astronomy	Grouping registries across fields to improve discoverability and best practices across research software repositories.	No single API -federates multiple registries	No	[60]
MyExperiment	Workflow sharing, bioinformatics	Early social platform for sharing scientific workflows (notably Taverna). Supports REST API, linked data, SPARQL.	REST API https://www.myexperiment.org/workflows.json	No	[61]
Research Software Directory	Multi-domain / institutional	Local or centralized registries of institutional research software. Often part of broader resource directories.	GraphQL API https://research-software-directory.org/graphql	No	[62]
rOpenSci	R / Data Science	Ecosystem and portal for R packages and tools in open science (with curated packages).	REST API https://ropensci.org/packages.json	No	[62]
Zenodo (Software community)	General research software	General research repository enabling DOI assignment for software; acts as informal registry and archive.	REST API https://zenodo.org/api/records/?communities=software	May be present in DataCite metadata	[62]

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HAL (France)	Multidisciplinary (French academia)	Open archive where researchers deposit outputs, including software (often with metadata).	OAI-PMH & REST API https://api.archives-ouvertes.fr/search?q=software	Input/output types not systematically recorded.	[62]
SciCrunch / RRID Portal	Biological research resources	Provides Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) for research tools, software, antibodies, cell lines—enhancing reproducibility through standard identifiers.	API documentation https://scicrunch.org/api/1/ (requires key)	No	[63]
ROHub	Reproducibility-focused registry of RO-Crates	RO-Hub acts as a repository that leverages RO-Crate to help publish, discover, and archive richly annotated Research Objects (ROs). Potentially contains links between tools and file types, workflows.	API Documentation https://reliance-eosc.github.io/ROHUB-API_documentation/html/	Yes Implicitly recorded	[77], [124]

6. Obtaining Data from Source

The majority of end users and systems first encounter a published research output, such as a dataset, via a landing page in a repository. They typically arrive there via three mechanisms:

1. Resolution of a PID for the dataset, for which a link to the landing page is usually the default resolution target [25];
2. Via a search in a metadata catalogue or aggregator;
3. Via a metadata description obtained via a harvester, usually requesting it through the OAI-PMH endpoint for the repository.

In all three of these cases, obtaining machine-actionable information about the files included in the dataset presents a challenge, since the implementation of such access varies considerably between implementations.

Unpublished datasets and their corresponding files are typically web accessible through download links provided directly from the end user, and this could be, for example, any valid `http://` or `ftp://` link. Several options are available for such access, each with advantages and disadvantages.

6.1. Local Data Sources

Irrespective of whether a prospective end user arrives at download links for individual files via metadata or direct sharing of a link, there are a number of protocols for such download links. Table 6.1.1 provides a summary of the most commonly implemented ones.

Table 6.1.1 Examples of Popular File Access Protocols

Method	Typical Use	Open	Notes	Reference
HTTP/HTTPS	Standard file downloads	Yes/ No	Most common, widely supported	[88]
FTP/FTPS	Legacy repositories	Yes/ No	Browsers dropped FTP, still in HPC/data centers	[89]
SFTP	Secure transfers	No Login required	Common in HPC/institutions	[90]
WebDAV	Collaborative storage	Yes/ No	Supported in Nextcloud/SharePoint	[91]
rsync	Repository mirroring	Yes	Efficient large-scale sync	[92]
Cloud links (S3, GCS, Azure)	Research datasets, APIs	Yes/ No	Signed URLs often used	[93]

BitTorrent	Large datasets, software ISOs	Yes	P2P, reduces server load	[94]
IPFS	Decentralised archiving	Yes	Content-addressed	[95]
Globus	Research data networks	No (account needed)	Large-scale, high-speed	[96]
OPeNDAP/ THREDDS	Earth science data	Yes	Subset and streaming support	[97]
ESGF	Earth science data	Yes	Provides multiple download protocols (HTTP, GridFTP, SFTP).	[98]

6.2. Mainstream Data Repository Software

The majority of repository software platforms provide access via HTTP, unless the data is sensitive or large, in which case other protocols may be more appropriate.

Table 6.2.1 lists the typical access options available for repositories and repository platforms involved in the initial Proof-of-Concept development phase in the EOSC Data Commons. As can be seen from the entries in the table, each repository implements a custom API for file access and download, indicating the need for a mediation service to assist with standardised methods of access.

Table 6.2.1: Data Access Methods for Repositories Participating in the Proof-of-Concept

Repository/ Platform	Download Options & API Support	Notes	Reference
Dataverse (DANS - 5 repositories)	Web UI: Files and datasets can be downloaded directly, with options to choose formats (e.g., original vs. archival). API: Data Access API allows programmatic download of files and full datasets (including format transformations like thumbnails or tabular exports).	Based on the Data Access API documentation (guides.dataverse.org)	[100]
Invenio / Zenodo	Web UI: Files can be downloaded individually or as part of records (plus DOI-based download via web) API: Zenodo (InvenioRDM) provides a REST API to list files, download/upload files programmatically.	Derived from Zenodo REST API docs (developers.zenodo.org) and migration notes (Invenio)	[101], [102]
DABAR (Croatian National Repository)	Web UI: Users can download uploaded objects (e.g., theses, articles) API: REST API available. DABAR supports a fully implemented REST API for repository functions, including (potentially) file operations—not just metadata ingestion.	Information based on general platform description (dabar.srce.hr , EOSC Association)	[103], [106]

HAL (France National Repo)	Web UI: Direct download of deposited documents (public). API: HAL provides a robust RESTful API (HAL v3.0) supporting search and metadata retrieval. While file download endpoints aren't explicit, the API supports listing records, from which download URLs can be derived.	As per HAL API documentation (api.archives-ouvertes.fr)	[104]
SWISSUbase	Web UI: Dataset downloads available depending on licensing and permissions (open, restricted, or upon request). API: Available, does not support file downloads.	Based on documentation and user guide excerpts (SWISSUbase) Public API and documentation available.	[105]

6.3. File Metadata and Manifests

For the vast majority of repositories, resolving a PID to the point where a file manifest is available with the most important file metadata (e.g. access restrictions, size, type, download link, checksum) is not only difficult from a machine-readable perspective, it is also highly diverse in its implementation. Figure 6.3.1 highlights the typical processes and the impediments to machine actionability in these processes.

Figure 6.3.1: From PID to Manifest⁴⁰

A machine that wants to 'follow its nose' to ultimately obtain file-level metadata, as well as a download link, faces multiple possible implementation pathways, as we discuss below.

- There are four typical starting points:
 - A PID is available, and from this, one can typically follow one of three pathways.
 - The PID can be submitted to a resolver, which by default will redirect to a human-readable landing page. From that landing page, it may be possible to find a link to the machine-readable metadata, but it is not always predictable or certain, and it is not standardised.
 - If the PID implements the basic FDO recommendations [22], a redirect to the metadata schema (profile) will also be obvious to machines, and directly available.
 - Some metadata providers, notably DataCite and Crossref, implement content negotiation [25], which enables a machine to find the machine-readable metadata directly, provided the content negotiation syntax is known. This syntax is not standardised, and other PIDs, for example ARK, implement a different syntax called *inflection*.
 - A machine can end up at the landing page for a resource, in which case the same pathways are available as above, after a PID has resolved to a landing page.
 - A machine entry point can be a harvesting endpoint, as for example offered by the OAI-PMH protocol [110], in which case individual metadata records are available in machine-readable format, and often in more than one, as advertised by the OAI-PMH endpoint in a standard way.
 - If a repository name is known, but nothing more, a machine can consult a registry such as [re3data](https://www.re3data.org/)⁴¹, which optionally lists an OAI-PMH endpoint. The usability of this property varies for machines, since the URL may not be present, is sometimes out of date, or the URL points to human-readable documentation or an instruction page, which cannot reliably be interpreted by machines. It is also not always guaranteed that a text label for a repository will unambiguously match a re3data entry. Hence this pathway is possibly automatable, but with a low expectation of success.
- Once a machine ends up at an encoded metadata record, there remains a number of impediments and variations.
 - Metadata schemas do not reference the object(s) or resource(s) they describe in a standardised way. This means that a mapping inventory is required to indicate to machines which element to consult to obtain information about the associated object(s) or resource(s). These mappings

⁴⁰ High-resolution version:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1w2VBkP1S3e5e0-67-zwAHYTvF8tbVKMw5CithSMob08>

⁴¹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

- should be configured and not hardcoded, and ideally be sourced from an authoritative inventory of schema crosswalks such as [MSCR](#)⁴².
 - In some cases, for example in the Dataverse platform, the link is indirect. Each metadata record has an internal ID, and this ID, not the PID, must be used to access file-level information through the Data API. While this pathway is reliably machine-actionable, the implementation is quite specific and needs to be configured before it can be used by machines.
- Once a list of one or more objects has been obtained (a 'manifest'), there are also significant differences in implementation. Manifests, for a start, do not all contain the same file-level metadata, and the schema in which it is offered are repository-specific. The contents, though, are machine-readable by definition.
- Obtaining a download link is the last step, and depending on the access restrictions, obtaining permission sometimes involves human assessment of the request, which of course breaks the machine-actionable sequence.

The diversity and impediments described above have solutions, but these all require repositories and/ or PID providers to implement additional functionality. These solutions are discussed below, and depicted in Figure 6.3.2.

Figure 6.3.2: From PID to Manifests - Removing Friction⁴³

There are three solutions that aim to remove friction to machine actionability in these pathways, all with varying degrees of implementation and scope of improvements:

⁴² <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/metadata-schema-and-crosswalk-registry-mscr>

⁴³ High-resolution version:

<https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1w2VBkP1S3e5e0-67-zwAHYTvF8tbVKMw5CithSMob08>

- Some **Metaresolvers**, for example the [FAIRCORE4EOSC MetaResolver](#)⁴⁴, inspect either the FDO record at source (identifier metadata), or content negotiation options, and based on this, indicate to machines which of the human-readable landing page, machine-readable metadata, or in some cases links to a file manifest or the object itself, are available. This enables machines to directly select the desired target in a repeatable and standardised way starting from a PID only.
- Repositories can implement one or both of two related specifications:
 - **Signposting** [23], [24], [110] utilise existing standards to return machine-actionable links in the HEAD request of a web-based resource, and as such, machines that start from a human-readable landing page will always reliably find links that are of interest to them - links to the metadata schema, a data API, or the repository OAI-PMH endpoint can all be encoded, in addition to many others. Implementation is simple, but has to be done at repository level. Signposting, once implemented, is likely highly reliable, since it is curated locally and mostly updated automatically.
 - **FAIRiCAT** [111] is a repository-level equivalent of Signposting, and specifies the way in which links to repository-level resources can be made machine-actionable. The endpoint for OAI-PMH harvesting is an obvious resource link, but other repository attributes can also be included [1].

RO-Crate [17] solves the problem of machine actionability by providing both the metadata and the file manifests associated with a digital object in a JSON-LD based standard schema. RO-Crate, though, is not housed in repositories, and individual packages are stored and curated wherever they are needed. An RO-Crate package does not have a PID and is not findable through PID resolution.

There has been discussion and growing consensus on how to integrate the obvious benefits of RO-Crate with Signposting [113], and this would then define the following highly efficient and reliable pathways:

- A PID resolves to a landing page, and the Signposting Linkset at that location points to an RO-Crate representation (this can be dynamically constructed from metadata and file manifests, and will always be up to date as a result).
- A bot arriving at a landing page for a resource can navigate directly to the RO-Crate representation of that resource, following the same pathway.

[Appendix C](#) summarises the scope of file metadata that should be included in manifests, together with implementation options.

DANS has started development work on a [File Metadata Harvester](#)⁴⁵, extending the [DataHugger](#)⁴⁶ project. This work will be continued and refined to create an operational

⁴⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-pid-meta-resolver-pidmr>

⁴⁵ <https://filemetrix.labs.dansdemo.nl/docs#>

⁴⁶ <https://j535d165.github.io/datahugger/>

service for the Metadata Warehouse and Type Registry to use. [Appendix D](#) summarises the most common MIME Types in the repositories participating in the Proof-of-Concept phase.

Chapter 8 takes these inputs into consideration to make design recommendations in respect of file metadata and manifest retrieval by machines on the basis of a PID. Such file-level metadata is at the root of matching with tools and platforms, since the types need to be known (unambiguously mapped to URIs), file sizes and types may affect suitability for specific tools and platforms, and the download links are required to prepare for deployment in the Data Player.

7. Definition of Deployment Platforms

7.1. Options for Deployment

There are many options for deployment of code and data for the purpose of processing or analysis, already described in some detail in Section 5.1. What is clear from the initial description is that some form of typology, coupled to a platform metadata schema, is required to capture the diversity of targets for deployment, and to ensure that selection is possible given appropriate parameters.

We expect that vocabularies will be needed to describe the following characteristics of deployment platforms:

- The locus of deployment: local, to a network-accessible server, to a cloud-based infrastructure, to an HPC environment, and similar distinctions. Not all tools can be deployed to all loci.
- The deployment type: some tools and services are permanently hosted and can for example be accessed via an API, some are available on a platform but have to be provisioned and deployed on demand, and some are deployed when requested from an external source.

7.2. Platform Metadata

The [EGI Infrastructure Manager](https://www.egi.eu/service/infrastructure-manager/)⁴⁷ uses TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) [114], an OASIS standard, to describe computing infrastructures in a portable way.

TOSCA describes what components make up a platform (nodes), how they connect (relationships), what they provide/ require (capabilities & requirements), how they should behave (policies & workflows), and what goes in/out (inputs/outputs & artifacts). These elements are described with identifiers and metadata for identification and reuse, and encoded as a YAML file.

There are several alternatives to TOSCA (See Table 7.2.1), but in the light of the fact that the Infrastructure Manager approach is likely to be adapted and adopted in the EOSC Data Commons project for the purposes of describing processing and computational platforms, it is a front-runner in respect of a basis for description of platforms. We have to bear in mind, though, that TOSCA will not be capable of or appropriate for description of other deployment targets, such as Jupyter Notebooks, or VREs. However, this can be achieved with the addition of custom nodes and proper support in the TOSCA runtime engine (e.g. Infrastructure Manager).

⁴⁷ <https://www.egi.eu/service/infrastructure-manager/>

Table 7.2.1: Options for Description of Computational and Workflow Platforms

Schema / Standard	Purpose / Description	Use Case / Strength	Adoption / Prevalence	References
TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications)	Declarative description of cloud/infrastructure topologies and their orchestration. Supports intent/goal-based modeling.	Supply chain of VRE/infrastructure deployments across heterogeneous and federated clouds. Enables platform portability and automation.	Widely used in European e-infrastructure: EGI's Infrastructure Manager (IM) uses TOSCA in production; implemented in INDIGO DataCloud, EOSC Hub, EOSC Beyond, EOSC Synergy, AI4EOSC and adopted by INFN Cloud, EOSC EU Node.	[115], [116], [118]
TOSCAdata (extension)	Extension of TOSCA to model data-pipeline applications.	Enabling modeling of data-processing workflows within cloud/application templates.	Presented in research; less evidence of production adoption yet.	[117]
CWL (Common Workflow Language)	Standard for describing computational workflows: tools, inputs, outputs, compute requirements, containerisation.	Workflow portability and reproducibility across platforms and workflow engines.	Strong adoption in life-sciences and elsewhere; supported by many tools (Toil, Cromwell, REANA, Galaxy, etc.)	[114], [119], [120]
WDL (Workflow Description Language)	Similar to CWL, but originally tied to Cromwell engine, script-like syntax.	Used heavily in genomics and by Broad Institute pipelines.	Quite prevalent in genomics; more restricted ecosystem than CWL.	[119]
Nextflow DSL	Domain-specific language for workflows, with strong container and execution support.	Highly popular in bioinformatics for scalable pipelines.	Widespread in bioinformatics, though less standardized for cross-platform workflow exchange.	[119]
RO-Crate (related tooling)	Packaging of research data, metadata, and workflows together for portability and FAIRness.	Bundling of data+workflow descriptions for reproducibility.	Emerging adoption; mentioned in tooling landscape surveys.	[17]
DCAT-AP / EOSC Service Profiles	Metadata schema for cataloguing services (including computational services) using dataset catalog frameworks extended for compute.	To describe VREs and platforms in service directories, enabling discovery and access.	Required for services onboarded to the EOSC Marketplace; widely adopted in Europe.	[123], [124]

GA4GH TRS (Tool Registry Service)	API + schema for registering/sharing workflows/tools (CWL, WDL, Nextflow).	Enables discovery and access to workflow implementations across platforms.	Growing adoption within the GA4GH ecosystem.	[122]
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Based on the diversity, and the expectation that one would need to reference a variety of platform types, the recommended action is to create an aggregated metadata schema that can be used to describe platforms from a wide variety of sources, while retaining compatibility where possible with the metadata source.

In summary, the scope of platform metadata one expects to record, based on TOSCA, DCAT-AP, and other inputs from Table 7.2.1, are provisionally the following:

- **Identification and description**
 - A unique URI or PID to identify the platform.
 - Name, Description
 - Operator (institution), can be [ROR](https://ror.org/)⁴⁸ for research organisations.
- **Standards and artefacts**
 - Standards conformed to, including workflow standards
 - Discovery and invocation standards, for example to integrate with GA4GH or Galaxy.
- **Deployment Options**
 - A set of deployment option combinations supported by the platform.
- **Capabilities and execution**
 - Can be largely based on TOSCA **capabilities/requirements** and DCAT-AP service “endpoint/capability” patterns.
 - Also aspects such as container support, accelerators, and similar.
- **Limits/ Quotas**
 - Cross-cutting limitations , for example in respect of computational cost, file sizes, storage, CPU, or RAM limitations.
 - Properties/ policies and queue/account quotas on HPC and VREs.
- **Access**
 - Should probably be based on EOSC/DCAT-AP service profiles: authentication/authorisation, enrollment, usage policy.
- **Provenance and sources**
 - Source(s) of the metadata.

Chapter 8 makes some recommendations in respect of responsibilities for and scope of implementation.

⁴⁸ <https://ror.org/>

8. Design Considerations

8.1. Information Model

Chapters 3-7 have examined the landscape with respect to exchange of packages between services and repositories, type definitions and type registries for file objects included into these packages and into repository storage, tool registries and types, and the platforms that can be used as targets for deployment of data files and tools.

Figure 8.1.1: Information Model for Packages, Tools, Types, and Platforms

These inputs can be synthesised into an information model, which is useful for understanding conceptually how objects, agents and services are related, and forms the basis of API, registry, and schema specifications. Figure 8.1.1 summarises our synthesis.

In the diagram, we define the following:

- A **PID** (persistent identifier) is at the root of references to research objects, and typically points to a **Metadata** record for the object, either human or machine-readable. It optionally sometimes points to the **Object(s)** described by the **Metadata**, but rarely directly - rather by reference, since some of the individual **Object(s)** may be subject to access management and control.
- The research **Object(s)**, typically a file or files of some type, is usually referenced in the metadata, and this should provide a mechanism for reaching the individual **Object(s)** based on the **PID**. In practice, there are many pathways to achieve this, and some of them are not automatable. See section 6.3 for a detailed discussion on this topic. Moreover, the elements that describe the links to **Object(s)** are not standardised and depend on the **Metadata Schema**.
- For purposes of exchange of **Object(s)** and their **Metadata**, these are packaged into one of many standard encodings, based on **Package Specifications**.
- Such **Packages** typically include the **Metadata** of the **Object(s)**, the **Object(s)** either by **File Reference** or the **Physical File(s)**, together with **File Properties**. A list of **File References** and their **File Properties** are referred to as a **File Manifest** (not shown).
- **Package Specifications** do not explicitly allow encoding of the **Tool(s)** to be applied on the **File** contents of the **Package**, but some encode the **Tool(s)** that were used to create the **File(s)**. This capability can be extended to include the **Tool(s)** identified by the end user for processing or analysing the **File(s)** in the **Package**.
- **Tools** have **Tool Properties**, such as their computational, memory, and operating system requirements.
- To determine which **Tool(s)** may be included in a **Package** containing **File Reference(s)**, a match is made between **Tool** input specifications, which reference one or more **File Type(s)**. To unambiguously define such a **File Type** depends on a variety of factors, and depending on the domain and format of the file, various sources must be used in combination to define a **File Type**.
- These sources include authoritative registries (IANA/ **MIME Type**, **EDAM**, and **PRONOM**), which may contain cross-references to one another.
- Some **File Types**, but not all, can be positively identified by a **File Signature**, which would typically be a bit sequence expected at a given location in the object bitstream.
- Some **File Types** need to be qualified additionally via **Schema** and **Profile** references, and some **File Types** can be specialisations (or generalisations) of others.
- Some **Platforms** may express a list of **Tool(s)** that they already host, or allow to be deployed, and some **Tool(s)** can contain references to the **Platforms** where they can be deployed.
- A **Package** that identifies the **Tool(s)** to be used, and is able to deliver either the **Physical Files** or mechanisms for obtaining them, can be submitted to a **Platform** for deployment and execution.
- **Platforms** have **Platform Properties**, and these can be matched with both **Tool Properties** and **File Properties** to pre-determine feasibility of deployment and execution.
- **Tools** can also indicate compatibility with a **Platform Type** that may determine feasibility of deployment.

This information model will form the basis of our design and specification efforts.

8.2. Package Exchange

The following design considerations are derived from Chapter 3, and summarised in Table 8.2.1.

Table 8.2.1: Package Exchange Design Considerations

#	Label	Description
8.2.1.1	Submission Packages	A sizable number of repositories accept submissions (SIPs) based on the BagIt specification. The Sword protocol, which accepts BagIt deposits, is the de facto standard for automated deposits to repositories, and is used by Dataverse, Invenio, Open Science Framework, FigShare, and many other repository platforms.
8.2.1.2	Dissemination Packages and Processing	In contrast, a growing number of data processing platforms accept RO-Crate packages, and recording of provenance is explicitly offered, and one should encourage repositories to support this dissemination method. RO-Crate is capable of describing additional context in an extensible way, and it can accommodate references to code, software, tools, processing platforms, file properties, and other considerations due to its extensibility.
8.2.1.3	Hybrids	Both the above have pros and cons when considering use of packages throughout the life cycle of an object, and as a result, hybrid approaches with tooling for interconversion between a RO-Crate encoding and a BagIt encoding will be quite useful and maximise utility. In these implementations, the RO-Crate encoding includes a file manifest with enough information to enable the recreation of the data/ section in a BagIt encoding, and the BagIt encoding, based on the BigBag specification [26], contains the physical objects, as well as an additional metadata file containing the entire RO-Crate (ro-crate-metadata.json).
8.2.1.4	Encoding Software and Tools	RO-Crate allows references to software and tools, but in the context of provenance (i.e. it was used in producing the data file(s) in the package). RO-Crate is extensible, and by properly defining a JSON-LD relation that captures the to-be-used software or tools, and the platforms to deploy to, RO-Crate can accommodate these too. BagIt does not provide for these references, but it can be included in the BigBag extension by embedding RO-Crate in a BagIt package.
8.2.1.5	Provenance	Utilise the existing capabilities of RO-Crate to record provenance in respect of processes executed by the Data Player. This serves as an input for submission of derived datasets.
8.2.1.6	Encoding Additional File Metadata	The BagIt specification does not directly allow inclusion of additional file metadata, but this can be encoded using the 'sidecar' method, by including a secondary file manifest. RO-Crate is extensible and can accommodate additional file metadata.
8.2.1.7	Signposting	Repositories should implement Signposting with RO-Crate support [113], with the RO-Crate support based on the extensions defined above. This significantly reduces the friction in navigating from PIDs to file-level metadata, and to including such information in a

	dissemination package based on RO-Crate.
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8.3. Type Registry

The following design considerations are derived from Chapter 4, and summarised in Table 8.3.1.

Table 8.3.1: Type Registry Design Considerations

#	Label	Description
8.3.1.1	Multiple Authoritative Sources	Unique and unambiguous definitions of file types are maintained in multiple sources (IANA/ MIMEDB, PRONOM, EDAM), and these have to be harmonised in a graph-like registry structure that retains LOD references to the original definitions. These have to be harvested from time to time to keep the harmonised registry up to date. WikiData can serve as a backup URI source for files not defined elsewhere, and often provides a link between the other sources.
8.3.1.2	Specialisation and Generalisation	Some file types are specialisations of others, and can be processed by tools that ingest the generalised type, even though an explicit link is not defined. The registry graph needs to maintain information on these relations and offer a mechanism for obtaining the generalisations associated with a file type through multiple hierarchical layers.
8.3.1.3	Schemas and Profiles	In many cases, specification of a File Type may not be precise enough to guarantee compatibility with a software application or tool, since a specific schema and possibly a profile of such a schema is expected as input. The registry graph needs to accommodate this added complexity.
8.3.1.4	Repository Practices	Repositories need to define the precise File Type at submission and ingest time, since precise matching types to tools depend on this aspect.
8.3.1.5	'File Typing' Assistance	There will be a need to assist researchers and repository managers with 'File Typing' - in other words, identifying the MIME Type (this could be done via fingerprinting as offered by DROID), defining any applicable schema and profiles (this can be done by inspecting the file for JSON-LD relationships in case of text files), and by matching PRONOM and EDAM references (can be done on the basis of named entity recognition and heuristics involving the file extension). This capability is not explicitly in scope for the project, but can be offered as a beta version API implementation.
8.3.1.5	Type Registry Content	The Type Registry needs to contain entries for at least all MIME Types, all EDAM and PRONOM types, and all types identified in the harvesting of file metadata from participating repositories. This content will be updated from time to time during the course of the project, but once operational, there is a curation responsibility on the provider of the Type Registry service - most likely an EOSC Node.
8.3.1.6	Preferred File Formats	Repositories and/ or domains can set up profiles of preferred formats, based on an initial curated harvest of guidance services. KNAW-DANS File Preferences API can be extended to provide the

		service.
8.3.1.7	Implement a Type Registry	This can be done with the FAIRCORE4EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR) as a basis, or by extending the KNAW-DANS Type Registry.
8.3.1.8	File Metadata Service	A file metadata service is required to assist with populating RO-Crate manifests and request packages, as well as indexing of the Metadata Warehouse until such time that participating repositories can implement Signposting (8.2.1.7).

8.4. Tool Registry

The following design considerations are derived from Chapter 5 and summarised in Table 8.4.1.

Table 8.4.1: Tool Registry Design Considerations

#	Label	Description
8.4.1.1	Tools Vocabulary	A set of vocabularies is required to describe aspects of tool metadata, including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Typology of value addition • Type of deployment (on demand, prepared, new deployment, ...) • Platform typology (local, VRE, container, HPC, ...)
8.4.1.2	CodeMeta Extensions	CodeMeta is the preferred basis for metadata descriptions of tools, but needs to be extended to accommodate deployment-related elements supported by the vocabularies described in 8.4.1.1.
8.4.1.3	Catalogue of Tools	A Catalogue of Tools must be developed based on the CodeMeta extensions (8.4.1.2). This is new development, with no existing platform suitable for extension.
8.4.1.4	Harvesting and Curating Tools	Tool definitions must be harvested from the most authoritative sources identified in Chapter 5. The harvested data is transformed to the extended CodeMeta schema, and synchronised with the Catalogue of Tools.
8.4.1.5	Metadata Crosswalks	Several useful crosswalks have been developed to convert software and tool metadata to CodeMeta, these will be directly useful.
8.4.1.6	Automated Annotation	Very few tool registries define input file types explicitly, and human curation of these relationships will not be possible due to scale. Mechanisms need to be explored to develop automated annotation, possibly including AI/ ML, to address this deficiency.

8.5. File Metadata

The following design considerations are derived from Chapter 6, and summarised in Table 8.5.1.

Table 8.5.1: File Metadata Design Considerations

#	Label	Description
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8.5.1.1	Existing Prototype	DANS has developed a prototype for File Metadata retrieval ⁴⁹ on the basis of a PID, this needs refinement and extension for use by both the Catalogue of Tools/ Type Registry (it determines the minimum content of the Type Registry by collecting the file extensions of all data files in participating repositories, the download links, as well as other file metadata). This will be refined and used by the Metadata Warehouse too as a basis for indexing.
8.5.1.2	Signposting Integration	The retrieval of file metadata on the basis of a PID will be fully automated, always synchronised, and highly reliable for those repositories that implement Signposting, and the File Metadata retrieval API can be refactored to make use of Signposting if available. These considerations are elaborated in detail in Chapter 6.

8.6. Platform Description

The following design considerations are derived from Chapter 7, and summarised in Table 8.6.1.

Table 8.6.1: Package Exchange Design Considerations

#	Label	Description
8.6.1.1	Platform Metadata	Collaboration is required with WP6 to design a metadata schema for Platform description, allowing the broad scope of content discussed in Chapter 7 to be accommodated, and for harvesting from widely adopted sources such as TOSCA, WDL, and DCAT-AP/ EOSC.
8.6.1.2	Vocabularies	Vocabularies to classify and describe deployment options are required to support the Platform Metadata Schema.
8.6.1.3	Harvesting	At this point, it is not clear whether the Catalogue of Tools will have responsibility for harvesting and maintaining an inventory or registry of Platforms, but this appears to be the natural choice, since the results need to be linked to Tools and included into the underlying graph data.

8.7. Summary of Recommendations

The recommendations and design considerations listed in this section can be summarised as follows:

- **Work Package 4**
 - Metadata Warehouse
 - Make use of the File Metadata Harvester, prototyped by DANS, to index metadata in the Metadata Warehouse on File Type and whether the type is determined explicitly or by imputation.
 - Once Signposting is available from participating repositories, implement dynamic harvesting of File Types.
- **Work Package 5**

⁴⁹ <https://filemetrix.labs.dansdemo.nl/docs#>

- Graph Database: A graph or graph-like database will be required as the backbone of the Catalogue of Tools, Type Registry, File Metadata, and Platform metadata content.
- Type Registry
 - Define a harmonising specification for a graph-like registry to record File Type information in sufficient detail to allow its precise matching with the tools, workflows, and code that can use those types as input;
 - Type Registry: Design and implement a Type Registry, with frequent harvesting from the proposed source registries, based on an algorithm that maximises automation and linking of source URIs.
 - The Type Registry must contain enough contextual information to support future AI-based matching of file objects for which typing has not been explicitly done to the most appropriate File Type.
 - Harvest file preferences from the indicated sources, and extend the KNAW-DANS Type Preference API to accommodate repository profiles.
 - Make a decision in respect of using the FAIRCORE4EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR) as a basis for a Type Registry.
 - Implement the File Type Harvester, extending the prototype that is already available. Once Signposting is available from any participating repository, the automation can be improved.
- Request Packager
 - Define an extended specification for BigBag implementation, and a companion extended RO-Crate specification that can accommodate references to Data Types in file metadata, additional file metadata that will be required by processing platforms; and are capable of recording tools and platforms selected for processing.
 - Package interconversion service: BigBag to RO-Crate, and vice versa.
- Catalogue of Tools
 - Extend the CodeMeta specification to accommodate description of tools to cover at least the tool inventory harvested for the scope of the project.
 - Tools Vocabulary: design and curate the vocabularies required for support of CodeMeta extensions.
 - Harvest tool definitions from the main sources identified in the design considerations, and implement CodeMeta crosswalks/ develop crosswalks where needed.
 - Curate the direct relationships between tools and file types.
 - Develop the Catalogue of Tools, based on CodeMeta extensions.
 - Agree with WP6 on a metadata schema and vocabulary for description of Platforms, and implement the harvesters and graph database content required to link Tools and Platforms.
- **Work Package 6**
 - Data Player: Implement provenance and context documentation in RO-Crate for outputs of Data Player processing. This serves as a basis for submission to a target repository, and as a basis for FAIR assessment of the submission.

- Platform Registry
 - Platform Type Vocabulary: collaborate with WP5 to define a vocabulary for description of platform types.
 - Platform metadata specification: not all platforms can be adequately described using TOSCA, and the design considerations involved in describing a full range of platforms needs to be synthesised into a platform metadata specification.
 - Consider FAIRiCAT as a mechanism for exposing Platform attributes; pointing to the relevant platform metadata.
- **Use Case Repositories**
 - Typing: repositories should implement type URIs provided by the Type Registry to improve indexing and matching.
 - Signposting: repositories should implement signposting with RO-Crate extensions, enabling machine-actionability in respect of package composition and metadata harvesting.
 - Accepting BagIt/ BigBag or RO-Crate Deposits: those repositories that will accept deposits of derived datasets, and/ or require FAIR assessment of submissions, will have to implement measures to accept standardised submissions.
 - FAIR Assessment: The basis of FAIR assessment prior to publication will be a standardised submission package, as described previously. FAIR assessment of existing published datasets will be based on the PID of the dataset, and Signposting will improve the success and precision of the assessment.
 - FAIRiCAT: This allows metadata harvesting endpoints and other repository attributes to be discovered and acted upon by machines, and improves the accuracy and precision of the information.

Next steps include application of these recommendations in specifications (due end September, 2025 as Milestone 14), and partial implementation in the Proof-of-Concept APIs, due end November 2025.

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Appendix A: Mapping Domain File Types

Table A.1 provides an example of the typical mappings that are required between domain-defined file types and MIME Types. The examples are based on synonyms recorded for EDAM [57] types, and on geospatial data formats referenced in [WikiData](#)⁵⁰.

Table A.1: Mapping Domain File Types to MIME Types

Registry	File format	Description	Source URI	IANA MIME type
EDAM	FASTA	File format used to store nucleotide or amino acid sequences	http://edamontology.org/format_1929	(none official); often text/x-fasta (unofficial)
EDAM	FASTQ	Nucleic acid sequence and base qualities file format	http://edamontology.org/format_1930	(none official); sometimes text/x-fastq (unofficial)
EDAM	SAM	Sequence Alignment/Map	http://edamontology.org/format_2572	(none official); sometimes text/x-sam
EDAM	BAM	Binary Sequence Alignment/Map	http://edamontology.org/format_2573	(none official); sometimes application/x-bam
EDAM	CRAM	Reference-based compression of alignment format.	http://edamontology.org/format_3464	(none official)
EDAM	VCF	Variant Call Format (VCF) is a tabular format for storing genomic sequence variations	http://edamontology.org/format_3016	(none official); sometimes text/x-vcf
EDAM	GFF3	Generic Feature Format version 3 (GFF3) of sequence features	http://edamontology.org/format_1975	(none official); sometimes text/x-gff3
EDAM	BED	Format of sequence annotation track, typically to be displayed in a genome browser	http://edamontology.org/format_3003	(none official)

⁵⁰ https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

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EDAM	Newick	Phylogenetic tree Newick (text) format	http://edamontology.org/format_1910	(none official)
EDAM	JSON	JavaScript Object Notation format	http://edamontology.org/format_3464	application/json
EDAM	CSV	Tabular data represented as comma-separated values in a text file	http://edamontology.org/format_3752	text/csv (official IANA)
EDAM	XML	eXtensible Markup Language (XML) format	http://edamontology.org/format_2330	application/xml (official IANA)
EDAM	HDF5	HDF5 is a data model, library, and file format for storing and managing data	http://edamontology.org/format_3590	(none official); sometimes application/x-hdf5
EDAM	NetCDF	Network Common Data Form (NetCDF)	http://edamontology.org/format_3469	(none official); sometimes application/x-netcdf
(Geospatial)	GeoJSON	JSON-based geospatial features format	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5533904	application/geo+json (IANA-registered)
(Geospatial)	Shapefile	ESRI vector format (.shp, .shx, .dbf, etc.)	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q27486884	application/vnd.shp, application/vnd.shp.shx, application/vnd.dbf (unstandardized)
(Geospatial)	GeoPackage	SQLite-based GIS container (.gpkg)	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q22908624	application/geopackage+sqlite3 (IANA-registered)
(Geospatial)	GeoTIFF	Geospatial extension of TIFF raster format	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q1502796	image/tiff; application=geotiff (recommended)
(Geospatial)	KML / KMZ	XML-based geographic annotation format	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q79587	application/vnd.google-earth.kml+xml, application/vnd.google-earth.kmz
(Geospatial)	GML	OGC XML-based spatial data exchange format	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q926165	application/gml+xml (common, not always officially registered)
(Geospatial)	MapInfo TAB	MapInfo vector format (TAB, DAT, MAP)	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q6753724	No standard MIME; often application/x-mapinfo-tab

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(Geospatial)	Others (e.g. NTF, SOSI, DXF)	Various national or CAD formats		Varies; typically not IANA-registered
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Appendix B: Preferred File Format Resources

Table B.1: Resources - Preferred Format Guidelines and API Endpoints

Resource	Scope	Content	Notes	Access	Website	Reference	
Library of Congress – Sustainability of Digital Formats	Widely used global reference for audiovisual, images, text, datasets, 3D, GIS, etc.	Format descriptions, sustainability factors, MIME mappings, references.	Provides HTML pages; no public API, but some data is structured enough to scrape.			https://www.loc.gov/preservation/digital/formats/	[76]
UK National Archives – PRONOM	Technical registry of file formats, software, and signatures.	File families (text, image, AV, GIS, 3D). Links to MIME, PUIDs.	No REST API, but widely used in preservation tools (DROID, Siegfried).	Bulk XML export	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/pronom.xml	[75]	
				Per-format URIs	https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/fmt/18		
NARA (US National Archives) – Transfer & Preservation Guidelines	Preferred formats for official US federal records (text, still images, AV, GIS, 3D).	Explicit “acceptable” vs. “preferred” formats for long-term access.	No API.			https://www.archives.gov/records-mgmt/policy/transfer-guidance	[78]
Open Preservation Foundation (OPF) – File Format Policies / Registries	Community-driven preservation best practices.	Hosts COPTR (Community Owned digital Preservation Tool Registry) which includes format guidance and	No API, but structured wiki.			https://coptr.digipres.org/	[79]

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		links.					
European Commission – EUDAT B2SHARE / EOSC Guidance	Recommends file formats for FAIR data deposition across scientific domains.	Guidance lists preferred file types for tabular, geospatial, audiovisual, etc.	No dedicated API for file format guidance.			https://eosc-portal.eu	[80]
Dataverse Community – File Handling & Formats	File families supported by Dataverse (tabular, GIS, audio, video, images).	Provides explicit support and recommendations (e.g., Shapefile, GeoTIFF, NetCDF for geospatial).		API Guide Endpoint to list file types	https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/api/native-api.html		[81]
					GET /api/info/metrics/filetypes (aggregated, not full spec).		
Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) – Technology Watch & Guidance	High-level format family guidance for archives (text, AV, GIS, 3D).	Not a registry, but publishes format-focused Technology Watch Reports.	No API.			https://www.dpconline.org/knowledge-base/tech-watch-reports	[82]
FITS (File Information Tool Set) + JHOVE	Format identification and validation (esp. for archives).	Encodes preferred/preservation formats into validation rules.	No registry API; runs locally to identify file types.			https://jhove.openpreservation.org/	[83]

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PLANETS / SCAPE / Archivemática policies	Preservation planning tools with configurable “format policies.”	Define preferred/acceptable formats at institutional level, often exported/sharable.	Provides JSON endpoints.		https://fpr.archivemática.org/		[84]
Harvard Library File Format Guidelines	Practical guidance across AV, text, images, GIS.		No API.			https://wiki.harvard.edu/confluence/display/DigPres/File+Formats+for+Long-Term+Preservation	[85]
KNAW-DANS	Recommended file formats for specific file groups and domains, covering dissemination and long-term preservation considerations	Guidance documentation supported by an API	API	API	https://type.labs.dans.knaw.nl/docs#/	https://dans.knaw.nl/en/file-formats/	[86], [87]

Table B.2: Example Long-Term Preservation Formats

File Family	Preferred Formats	MIME Type(s)	Notes (LoC / NARA / PRONOM)
Text / Documents	PDF/A, PDF 1.4+	application/pdf	PDF/A not separately registered in MIME; handled as application/pdf. PRONOM distinguishes PDF versions.
Text / Documents	Plain text (UTF-8)	text/plain	Universally supported.
Text / Documents	XML	application/xml	Base for many domain standards (e.g., TEI, METS, MODS).

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Text / Documents	ODF (ODT)	application/vnd.oasis.opendocument.text	Preferred over DOCX for openness.
Tabular / Spreadsheets	CSV, TSV	text/csv, text/tab-separated-values	CSV = IANA registered; TSV is widely used but not formally registered.
Tabular / Spreadsheets	ODS	application/vnd.oasis.opendocument.spreadsheet	Open alternative to XLS/XLSX.
Images (Raster)	TIFF (uncompressed, 6.0)	image/tiff	Gold standard (PRONOM fmt/353).
Images (Raster)	JPEG 2000 (lossless JP2)	image/jp2	IANA registered; preservation-favored if lossless.
Images (Raster)	PNG	image/png	Widely supported open raster format.
Images (Vector)	SVG	image/svg+xml	Open standard (W3C).
Images (Vector)	PDF/A (vector content)	application/pdf	Still most used archival vector wrapper.
Images (Vector)	EPS	application/postscript (sometimes application/eps)	Not formally IANA registered as EPS, but often used.
Audio	WAV / Broadcast WAVE (BWF)	audio/wav, audio/x-wav (unofficial), audio/vnd.wave (IANA)	LoC/NARA standard for audio masters.
Audio	FLAC	audio/flac (registered)	Lossless compressed preservation format.
Audio	AIFF	audio/aiff	IANA registered.
Video	Matroska (FFV1/FLAC)	video/x-matroska (official: video/matroska)	Open archival container; FFV1 codec widely adopted.
Video	Motion JPEG2000 (MXF)	video/mj2 or application/mxf	MJPEG2000: video/mj2; MXF: application/mxf.
Video	MP4 (H.264/AAC)	video/mp4	Accepted access format, not preservation-grade.
Geospatial (GIS)	GeoTIFF	image/tiff; application=geotiff (OGC)	Official extension of TIFF.

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Geospatial (GIS)	GeoPackage (.gpkg)	application/geopackage+sqlite3 (IANA)	OGC standard; SQLite-based container.
Geospatial (GIS)	Shapefile (.shp, .dbf, .shx)	(no official MIME; often application/x-shapefile)	Still widely used though legacy. PRONOM provides fmt identifiers.
Geospatial (GIS)	GML	application/gml+xml	OGC XML format.
Geospatial (GIS)	KML/KMZ	application/vnd.google-earth.kml+xml, application/vnd.google-earth.kmz	IANA registered.
3D / CAD	OBJ	(no IANA MIME; sometimes model/obj unofficial)	Simple geometry/text.
3D / CAD	PLY	(no IANA MIME; sometimes application/x-ply)	Used in 3D scanning.
3D / CAD	STL	model/stl (IANA registered 2019)	Widely used in 3D printing.
3D / CAD	X3D	model/x3d+xml	Official IANA MIME type.
3D / CAD	glTF	model/gltf+json, model/gltf-binary	IANA registered.
Scientific / Data Exchange	HDF5	(no official MIME; application/x-hdf5)	Widely used, PRONOM assigns fmt IDs.
Scientific / Data Exchange	NetCDF	application/netcdf (IANA registered)	Used with CF Conventions in climate science.
Scientific / Data Exchange	FITS (astronomy)	image/fits (IANA registered)	Longstanding archival standard.
Email / Messaging	MBOX	(no official MIME; sometimes application/mbox)	PRONOM has identifiers.
Email / Messaging	EML (RFC 5322)	message/rfc822	IANA registered.
Email / Messaging	PST (MS Outlook)	(no IANA MIME; application/vnd.ms-outlook)	Proprietary; discouraged for preservation.
Web / Markup	WARC	application/warc (IANA registered 2017)	ISO 28500 archival web format.

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Web / Markup	HTML5	text/html	Standard web format.
Web / Markup	CSS	text/css	Stylesheet.
Web / Markup	JavaScript	application/javascript	Registered MIME.

Appendix C: File Metadata

Table C.1: File Metadata Elements, Options, and Comparison

Metadata element	BagIt (RFC 8493)	RO-Crate	METS / PREMIS	WARC (ISO 28500)	Notes	Reference
File name / path	Yes (relative path in manifest-*.txt, data/)	Yes (@id of File entity, relative path)	Yes (<fileSec> with FLocat URI)	Yes (WARC-Target-URI, payload file path)	Fundamental across all manifests	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Download link (URI)	BagIt assumes local package	Yes (contentUrl or @id pointing to HTTP/FTP/etc.)	Yes (FLocat xlink:href)	Yes (WARC-Target-URI)	Important for remote access / FAIR context	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Size (bytes)	Not included by default (only checksums)	Yes (contentSize in bytes, schema.org/DataDownload)	Yes (<size> in PREMIS fixity)	Yes (Content-Length header)	BagIt omits size, but can be added in tag files	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Checksum / fixity	Yes (SHA-256, MD5, etc., in manifest)	Yes (checksum, sha256, etc., under Digest in JSON-LD)	Yes (fixity elements in PREMIS)	Yes (WARC-Payload-Digest, WARC-Block-Digest)	Strong across preservation systems	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
MIME type	Not in base specification	Yes (encodingFormat with MIME, PRONOM, EDAM, etc.)	Yes (<formatName> / <formatRegistry> with MIME, PRONOM PUID)	Yes (Content-Type HTTP header)	Only BagIt omits this	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]

Landscape Analysis for the Packaging Specification and Components

Domain-specific type (EDAM, PRONOM, Wikidata)	Not supported	Yes (any ontology via JSON-LD context, often EDAM/PRONOM)	Yes (PREMIS <formatRegistry> with PRONOM PUID)	No (limited to MIME / Content-Type)	RO-Crate most flexible	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Access restrictions / rights	Not in base specification	Yes (license, conditionsOfAccess, authorisation)	Yes (<rightsMD> in METS, PREMIS rights module)	No	Important for repositories, less so for archival crawls	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Provenance / creation metadata	Not in base specification	Yes (full provenance graph: creator, date, workflow)	Yes (PREMIS event, agent, object metadata)	Limited (crawl date, WARC headers)	Richest in RO-Crate & PREMIS	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Software / environment info	No	Yes (sdPublisher, softwareRequirements)	Yes (PREMIS <creatingApplication>)	Limited (user-agent strings in crawls)	Only structured in RO-Crate / PREMIS	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Identifiers (PIDs)	No	Yes (@id, DOI, Handle, ARK, etc.)	Yes (objectIdentifier in PREMIS)	Yes (WARC record IDs)	Helps cross-referencing with DOI/Handle	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
File hierarchy / structure	Implicit via directory paths	Explicit in JSON-LD (hierarchical relationships)	Yes (structMap in METS)	Limited (crawl sequence)	Hierarchy clearer in RO-Crate & METS	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]
Multiple checksum algorithms	Yes (can include manifest per algorithm, e.g., manifest-md5.txt, manifest-sha256.txt)	Yes (JSON-LD graph can include multiple digests)	Yes (PREMIS allows multiple fixities)	Limited to headers	BagIt excels here	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]

Landscape Analysis for the Packaging Specification and Components

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File Purpose or Role	No	Yes, JSON-LD relationships	No	No	Required to define e.g. that a file is a transcript or synthetic data equivalent of another	[8], [9], [10], [17], [99]

Appendix D: Distribution of MIME Types

Figure D.1 shows the count of MIME Types after a partial harvest of Proof-of-Concept repositories (the repositories participating in the Proof-of-Concept, which includes DANS - 5 repositories, DABAR, HAL, and SWISSUbase). To get this information in its latest form, use the following call: https://filemetrix.labs.dansdemo.nl/file-metadata/count/grouped/mime_type

MIME Type - Partial Harvest of Proof-of-Concept Repositories

Figure D.1: MIME Type Count for Proof-of-Concept Repositories